

Two- and Three-Dimensional Osteometric Variability of the Foramen Magnum in Modern Humans

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10038819

Supplementary material – S3 – Results

List of Contents

S3.1 – 3.2	TEM, %TEM and R Coefficient Values
S3.3	Bland-Altman Plots
S3.4	LCCC Microsoft Excel Codes
S3.5	LCCC Values
S3.6	LCCC Scatter Plots
S3.7	Centroid Radius Approach Results
S3.8	Error Shape-PCA Score Plots
S3.9	Residual Skewness & Kurtosis Values
S3.10 – 3.11	Residual Q-Q Plots
S3.12 – 3.13	Residual Histograms
S3.14	Shapiro-Wilk Test Results for Residuals
S3.15	Levene's Test Results for Residuals
S3.16 – 3.18	2D Summary Statistics
S3.19	Summary Statistics from the Published Literature
S3.20	Summarised Summary Statistics from Published Literature
S3.21	Foramen Magnum Shape Categories across the Published Literature
S3.22 – 3.25	PCA Scree-Plots and Shape- / Form-PCA Summary Report
S3.26 – 3.29	Extracted Shape- / Form-PC Score Values
S3.30 – 3.31	Allometric Regression and 2B-PLS Values
S3.32 – S3.34	Two-way ANOVA Test Results (2D FM Variables)

S3.35 – 3.36	Tukey's HSD Test Results (2D FM Variables)
S3.37 – 3.39	One-way ANOVA Test Results (2D FM Variables)
S3.40 – 3.41	Tukey's HSD Test Results (2D FM Variables)
S3.42 – 3.43	One- / Two-way Procrustes Shape ANOVA Results
S3.44 – 3.34	ANCOVA Test Results of the Full Allometric Models
S3.46 – 3.48	Univariate Range Plots of 2D FM Variables
S3.49 – 3.57	FML vs. FMB Scatter Plots
S3.58 – 3.61	FMI shape Category Frequency Plots & Tables
S3.62 – 3.67	Shape- / From-PC Score Scatter Plots
S3.68	PLS Scatter Plot of the Sex-Known Dataset

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.1

2D Intraobserver Error Analysis – Absolute and Relative Technical Measurement Error and Coefficient of Reliability of FML

Tab. S3.1: Calculations for the absolute (aTEM) and relative (%TEM) technical error of all repeated 2D FML measurements for the intraobserver error. See text for descriptions of the calculation. Calculations for the aTEM and %TEM for the three repetitions set have been performed using the pre-coded MS Excel spreadsheet by Langley et al. (2018), where their codes and column references have been adjusted accordingly to fit the present dataset. Codes for the two repetitions set have been coded in Excel by the author following the formula reported by Goto and Mascie-Taylor (2007).

Population	ID	Three Repetitions (physical and virtual measurements)						Two Repetitions (only physical measurements)			
		FML_1	FML_2	FML_B	$\sum_i^K M(n)^2$	$\frac{(\sum_i^K M(n))^2}{K}$	$\left[\sum_i^K M(n)^2 - \frac{(\sum_i^K M(n))^2}{K} \right]$	FML_1	FML_2	Difference (Δ)	Difference ² (Δ^2)
Eritrea	RV 1065	37.04	36.97	37.64	4155.51	4155.24	0.27	37.04	36.97	0.07	0.0049
Eritrea	RV 1283	31.82	31.88	32.48	3083.80	3083.53	0.27	31.82	31.88	-0.06	0.0036
Eritrea	RV 1284	37.82	37.84	37.94	4301.66	4301.65	0.01	37.82	37.84	-0.02	0.0004
Eritrea	RV 1285	35.21	35.33	36.11	3791.89	3791.41	0.48	35.21	35.33	-0.12	0.0144
Eritrea	RV 1288	35.64	35.86	36.66	3900.10	3899.53	0.58	35.64	35.86	-0.22	0.0484
Eritrea	RV 1289	30.69	30.76	31.16	2859.00	2858.87	0.13	30.69	30.76	-0.07	0.0049
Eritrea	RV 1290	32.47	32.48	32.80	3185.09	3185.02	0.07	32.47	32.48	-0.01	0.0001
Eritrea	RV 1291	38.34	38.36	38.53	4426.01	4425.98	0.02	38.34	38.36	-0.02	0.0004
Eritrea	RV 1293	36.71	36.57	36.78	4037.76	4037.73	0.02	36.71	36.57	0.14	0.0196
Eritrea	RV 1294	30.95	31.04	31.48	2912.37	2912.21	0.16	30.95	31.04	-0.09	0.0081
Eritrea	RV 1296	37.43	37.37	37.63	4213.54	4213.50	0.04	37.43	37.37	0.06	0.0036
Eritrea	RV 1298	37.79	37.90	38.73	4364.51	4363.98	0.53	37.79	37.90	-0.11	0.0121
Eritrea	RV 1300	41.79	41.95	42.38	5302.27	5302.08	0.19	41.79	41.95	-0.16	0.0256
Eritrea	RV 1301	32.10	32.36	33.00	3166.58	3166.15	0.43	32.10	32.36	-0.26	0.0676
Eritrea	RV 1302	37.59	37.52	37.75	4245.82	4245.79	0.03	37.59	37.52	0.07	0.0049
Eritrea	RV 1303	36.28	36.34	36.25	3950.90	3950.89	0.00	36.28	36.34	-0.06	0.0036
Eritrea	RV 1304	35.11	35.03	35.35	3709.44	3709.38	0.06	35.11	35.03	0.08	0.0064
Eritrea	RV 1305	34.71	34.68	35.55	3671.29	3670.80	0.49	34.71	34.68	0.03	0.0009
Eritrea	RV 1306	34.30	34.28	35.06	3580.81	3580.42	0.40	34.30	34.28	0.02	0.0004
Eritrea	RV 1307	31.55	31.34	31.99	3000.96	3000.74	0.22	31.55	31.34	0.21	0.0441
Eritrea	RV 1309	37.03	36.68	37.78	4143.97	4143.34	0.63	37.03	36.68	0.35	0.1225
Japan	RV 37	37.07	37.04	37.63	4162.16	4161.94	0.22	37.07	37.04	0.03	0.0009
Japan	RV 1067	37.12	37.80	37.08	4181.66	4181.33	0.33	37.12	37.80	-0.68	0.4624
Japan	RV 2148	32.98	33.02	33.26	3284.23	3284.18	0.05	32.98	33.02	-0.04	0.0016

Japan	S 4033	33.20	33.20	33.82	3348.27	3348.02	0.26	33.20	33.20	0.00	0.0000
Japan	S 4034	35.24	35.16	35.87	3764.74	3764.44	0.30	35.24	35.16	0.08	0.0064
Japan	S 4035	35.10	34.94	35.38	3704.56	3704.46	0.10	35.10	34.94	0.16	0.0256
Japan	S 4036	31.55	31.49	31.71	2992.55	2992.52	0.03	31.55	31.49	0.06	0.0036
Japan	S 4037	34.10	33.99	34.82	3530.56	3530.16	0.41	34.10	33.99	0.11	0.0121
Japan	S 4038	35.63	35.51	36.20	3840.90	3840.63	0.27	35.63	35.51	0.12	0.0144
Japan	S 4039	36.85	37.05	37.24	4117.44	4117.37	0.08	36.85	37.05	-0.20	0.0400
Japan	S 4632	36.80	36.75	37.07	4078.99	4078.93	0.06	36.80	36.75	0.05	0.0025
Germany	RV 376	40.19	40.15	40.58	4874.00	4873.88	0.11	40.19	40.15	0.04	0.0016
Germany	RV 389	33.28	33.28	33.69	3350.13	3350.02	0.11	33.28	33.28	0.00	0.0000
Germany	RV 613	37.36	37.31	38.07	4237.13	4236.77	0.36	37.36	37.31	0.05	0.0025
Germany	RV 614	39.23	39.33	39.75	4665.90	4665.75	0.15	39.23	39.33	-0.10	0.0100
Germany	RV 615	34.26	34.20	34.50	3533.64	3533.59	0.05	34.26	34.20	0.06	0.0036
Germany	RV 721	37.66	37.59	38.59	4320.47	4319.85	0.62	37.66	37.59	0.07	0.0049
Germany	RV 724	40.18	40.06	40.34	4846.55	4846.51	0.04	40.18	40.06	0.12	0.0144
Germany	RV 725	37.15	37.38	37.71	4199.43	4199.27	0.16	37.15	37.38	-0.23	0.0529
Germany	RV 726	32.64	32.83	33.24	3248.08	3247.89	0.19	32.64	32.83	-0.19	0.0361
Germany	RV 778	35.45	35.53	36.04	3817.97	3817.76	0.20	35.45	35.53	-0.08	0.0064
Germany	RV 782	36.37	36.33	36.57	3980.01	3979.98	0.03	36.37	36.33	0.04	0.0016
Germany	RV 783	35.62	35.51	36.25	3843.81	3843.49	0.32	35.62	35.51	0.11	0.0121
Germany	RV 786	38.83	38.79	39.43	4567.16	4566.90	0.26	38.83	38.79	0.04	0.0016
Germany	RV 834	32.98	32.90	33.44	3288.32	3288.15	0.17	32.98	32.90	0.08	0.0064
Germany	RV 870	39.63	39.60	40.06	4743.50	4743.37	0.13	39.63	39.60	0.03	0.0009
Germany	RV 872	34.86	34.84	35.90	3717.86	3717.12	0.74	34.86	34.84	0.02	0.0004
Germany	RV 879	34.08	34.03	34.79	3529.83	3529.47	0.36	34.08	34.03	0.05	0.0025
Germany	RV 884	34.75	34.59	35.05	3632.53	3632.42	0.11	34.75	34.59	0.16	0.0256
Germany	RV 886	35.12	34.96	35.75	3733.68	3733.33	0.35	35.12	34.96	0.16	0.0256
Germany	RV 890	39.61	39.58	40.21	4752.37	4752.12	0.25	39.61	39.58	0.03	0.0009
Germany	RV 899	36.78	36.99	36.86	4079.69	4079.67	0.02	36.78	36.99	-0.21	0.0441
Germany	RV 901	36.76	36.50	37.49	4089.05	4088.52	0.53	36.76	36.50	0.26	0.0676
Germany	RV 903	38.84	38.60	39.20	4535.15	4534.96	0.18	38.84	38.60	0.24	0.0576
Germany	RV 905	35.04	34.84	35.82	3724.70	3724.16	0.54	35.04	34.84	0.20	0.0400
Germany	RV 923	34.40	34.48	34.80	3583.27	3583.18	0.09	34.40	34.48	-0.08	0.0064
Germany	RV 959	35.06	35.03	35.81	3738.66	3738.27	0.39	35.06	35.03	0.03	0.0009
Germany	RV 1007	36.14	35.91	36.83	3952.08	3951.62	0.46	36.14	35.91	0.23	0.0529
Germany	RV 1124	37.44	37.39	38.81	4305.98	4304.68	1.30	37.44	37.39	0.05	0.0025
Germany	RV 1613	40.06	40.24	40.50	4864.31	4864.21	0.10	40.06	40.24	-0.18	0.0324
Germany	RV 1615	39.64	39.66	40.21	4761.09	4760.88	0.21	39.64	39.66	-0.02	0.0004
Germany	RV 1616	33.46	33.39	34.47	3422.64	3421.91	0.73	33.46	33.39	0.07	0.0049
Germany	RV 1618	32.50	32.35	32.92	3186.50	3186.32	0.17	32.50	32.35	0.15	0.0225
Germany	RV 1625	34.42	34.25	34.97	3580.70	3580.42	0.28	34.42	34.25	0.17	0.0289

Germany	RV 1630	38.14	38.33	39.15	4456.57	4455.99	0.58	38.14	38.33	-0.19	0.0361					
Germany	RV 1633	36.35	36.54	37.00	4025.49	4025.27	0.22	36.35	36.54	-0.19	0.0361					
Germany	RV 1636	38.11	38.05	38.41	4375.50	4375.43	0.07	38.11	38.05	0.06	0.0036					
Germany	RV 1638	31.04	30.84	31.28	2893.03	2892.93	0.10	31.04	30.84	0.20	0.0400					
Germany	RV 1639	38.00	38.03	38.67	4385.65	4385.36	0.29	38.00	38.03	-0.03	0.0009					
Germany	RV 1640	34.18	33.97	34.70	3526.32	3526.04	0.28	34.18	33.97	0.21	0.0441					
Germany	RV 1656	36.83	37.80	38.42	4261.39	4260.10	1.28	36.83	37.80	-0.97	0.9409					
Germany	RV 1657	34.76	34.77	35.01	3642.91	3642.87	0.04	34.76	34.77	-0.01	0.0001					
Germany	S 158	34.11	34.24	34.80	3546.91	3546.64	0.27	34.11	34.24	-0.13	0.0169					
Germany	S 159	39.12	39.38	39.80	4665.20	4664.96	0.24	39.12	39.38	-0.26	0.0676					
Germany	S 162	33.72	33.81	33.90	3429.36	3429.35	0.02	33.72	33.81	-0.09	0.0081					
Germany	S 4541	34.25	34.63	34.72	3577.78	3577.65	0.12	34.25	34.63	-0.38	0.1444					
Germany	S 4585	32.03	32.72	33.94	3248.44	3246.57	1.87	32.03	32.72	-0.69	0.4761					
Germany	S 4631	33.09	33.17	33.51	3318.12	3318.02	0.10	33.09	33.17	-0.08	0.0064					
Germany	S 5164	39.33	39.37	40.13	4707.26	4706.86	0.41	39.33	39.37	-0.04	0.0016					
Germany	S 5164	35.71	35.46	35.94	3824.30	3824.18	0.12	35.71	35.46	0.25	0.0625					
Greece	RSK 501	35.75	35.77	35.97	3851.40	3851.37	0.03	35.75	35.77	-0.02	0.0004					
Greece	RSK 502	36.79	36.34	37.20	4057.94	4057.57	0.37	36.79	36.34	0.45	0.2025					
Greece	RSK 503	35.04	34.93	35.39	3700.36	3700.24	0.12	35.04	34.93	0.11	0.0121					
Greece	RSK 504	30.37	30.15	30.76	2777.54	2777.35	0.19	30.37	30.15	0.22	0.0484					
Greece	RSK 505	35.69	35.60	36.39	3865.37	3864.99	0.37	35.69	35.60	0.09	0.0081					
Greece	RSK 506	37.02	37.05	37.38	4140.45	4140.37	0.08	37.02	37.05	-0.03	0.0009					
Greece	RV 1119	34.78	34.81	35.27	3665.36	3665.21	0.15	34.78	34.81	-0.03	0.0009					
Greece	RV 1120	36.26	36.29	36.93	3995.58	3995.29	0.29	36.26	36.29	-0.03	0.0009					
Greece	RV 1121	41.93	42.12	42.78	5362.35	5361.95	0.40	41.93	42.12	-0.19	0.0361					
Greece	RV 1122	34.38	34.28	34.70	3561.19	3561.10	0.10	34.38	34.28	0.10	0.0100					
Greece	RV 1123	38.15	38.06	38.34	4373.94	4373.90	0.04	38.15	38.06	0.09	0.0081					
Greece	RV 1842	39.75	39.76	40.87	4831.28	4830.45	0.83	39.75	39.76	-0.01	0.0001					
Greece	RV 1844	35.76	35.97	36.00	3868.62	3868.58	0.03	35.76	35.97	-0.21	0.0441					
Greece	RV 1845	30.86	30.35	31.10	2840.67	2840.38	0.29	30.86	30.35	0.51	0.2601					
Greece	RV 1846	31.46	31.65	32.05	3018.66	3018.48	0.18	31.46	31.65	-0.19	0.0361					
Greece	RV 1847	32.75	32.97	33.31	3269.14	3268.98	0.16	32.75	32.97	-0.22	0.0484					
Greece	RV 1848	35.28	35.22	35.36	3735.46	3735.45	0.01	35.28	35.22	0.06	0.0036					
Mean (all FML_1/2/M measurements):		35.88			Sum of all $\left[\sum_{i=1}^k M(n)^2 - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^k M(n))^2}{k} \right]$:			17.94			Mean (all FML_1/2 measurements):	35.70	Sum of all Δ^2:		4.1433	
SD (all FML_1/2/M measurements):		2.62									SD (all FML_1/2 measurements):	2.61				
aTEM of FML		0.37									0.15					
%TEM of FML		1.02%									0.41%					
R of FML		0.9804									0.9969					

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.2

2D Intraobserver Error Analysis – Absolute and Relative Technical Measurement Error and Coefficient of Reliability of FMB

Tab. S3.2: Calculations for the absolute (aTEM) and relative (%TEM) technical error of all repeated 2D FMB measurements for the intraobserver error. See text for descriptions of the calculation. Calculations for the aTEM and %TEM for the three repetitions set have been performed using the pre-coded MS Excel spreadsheet by Langley et al. (2018), where their codes and column references have been adjusted accordingly to fit the present dataset. Codes for the two repetitions set have been coded in Excel by the author following the formula reported by Goto and Mascie-Taylor (2007).

Population	ID	Three Repetitions (physical and virtual measurements)						Two Repetitions (only physical measurements)			
		FMB_1	FMB_2	FMB_B	$\sum_i^K M(n)^2$	$\frac{(\sum_i^K M(n))^2}{K}$	$\left[\sum_i^K M(n)^2 - \frac{(\sum_i^K M(n))^2}{K} \right]$	FMB_1	FMB_2	Difference (Δ)	Difference ² (Δ^2)
Eritrea	RV 1065	24.85	24.75	25.08	1859.09	1859.03	0.06	24,85	24,75	0,10	0,0100
Eritrea	RV 1283	26.58	26.55	27.06	2143.64	2143.48	0.16	26,58	26,55	0,03	0,0009
Eritrea	RV 1284	28.82	28.29	28.57	2447.16	2447.02	0.14	28,82	28,29	0,53	0,2809
Eritrea	RV 1285	28.63	28.73	28.99	2485.51	2485.44	0.07	28,63	28,73	-0,10	0,0100
Eritrea	RV 1288	30.25	30.19	30.17	2736.73	2736.72	0.00	30,25	30,19	0,06	0,0036
Eritrea	RV 1289	24.63	24.36	24.70	1810.14	1810.07	0.06	24,63	24,36	0,27	0,0729
Eritrea	RV 1290	28.35	28.35	28.26	2406.07	2406.07	0.01	28,35	28,35	0,00	0,0000
Eritrea	RV 1291	31.49	31.80	31.83	3016.01	3015.94	0.07	31,49	31,80	-0,31	0,0961
Eritrea	RV 1293	30.42	30.59	30.60	2797.48	2797.46	0.02	30,42	30,59	-0,17	0,0289
Eritrea	RV 1294	25.93	26.05	26.12	2033.22	2033.20	0.02	25,93	26,05	-0,12	0,0144
Eritrea	RV 1296	28.14	28.30	27.87	2369.49	2369.39	0.09	28,14	28,30	-0,16	0,0256
Eritrea	RV 1298	28.54	28.50	28.55	2441.88	2441.88	0.00	28,54	28,50	0,04	0,0016
Eritrea	RV 1300	35.38	35.40	35.79	3785.83	3785.72	0.11	35,38	35,40	-0,02	0,0004
Eritrea	RV 1301	27.95	28.01	28.01	2350.32	2350.32	0.00	27,95	28,01	-0,06	0,0036
Eritrea	RV 1302	28.71	28.05	28.17	2404.62	2404.37	0.25	28,71	28,05	0,66	0,4356
Eritrea	RV 1303	28.55	28.61	29.00	2474.63	2474.52	0.12	28,55	28,61	-0,06	0,0036
Eritrea	RV 1304	28.72	28.55	29.14	2489.08	2488.90	0.18	28,72	28,55	0,17	0,0289
Eritrea	RV 1305	27.30	27.20	27.22	2226.06	2226.05	0.01	27,30	27,20	0,10	0,0100
Eritrea	RV 1306	29.40	29.18	29.33	2576.08	2576.06	0.03	29,40	29,18	0,22	0,0484
Eritrea	RV 1307	27.06	27.11	27.30	2212.49	2212.45	0.03	27,06	27,11	-0,05	0,0025
Eritrea	RV 1309	30.13	30.19	30.02	2720.45	2720.44	0.01	30,13	30,19	-0,06	0,0036
Japan	RV 37	30.56	30.56	30.56	2801.74	2801.74	0.00	30,56	30,56	0,00	0,0000
Japan	RV 1067	30.67	30.88	31.18	2866.42	2866.28	0.13	30,67	30,88	-0,21	0,0441
Japan	RV 2148	26.92	27.01	27.47	2208.83	2208.65	0.17	26,92	27,01	-0,09	0,0081

Japan	S 4033	30.89	30.89	31.32	2889.33	2889.20	0.12	30,89	30,89	0,00	0,0000
Japan	S 4034	29.35	29.79	30.40	2673.03	2672.47	0.56	29,35	29,79	-0,44	0,1936
Japan	S 4035	32.22	32.85	33.30	3226.14	3225.55	0.59	32,22	32,85	-0,63	0,3969
Japan	S 4036	26.73	26.76	26.95	2156.89	2156.86	0.03	26,73	26,76	-0,03	0,0009
Japan	S 4037	29.61	29.82	29.88	2658.80	2658.76	0.04	29,61	29,82	-0,21	0,0441
Japan	S 4038	30.15	29.86	30.43	2726.63	2726.46	0.16	30,15	29,86	0,29	0,0841
Japan	S 4039	31.74	31.65	32.00	3033.15	3033.08	0.07	31,74	31,65	0,09	0,0081
Japan	S 4632	32.44	32.55	32.75	3184.42	3184.37	0.05	32,44	32,55	-0,11	0,0121
Germany	RV 376	31.57	30.97	31.15	2926.13	2925.94	0.19	31,57	30,97	0,60	0,3600
Germany	RV 389	28.66	28.91	29.03	2499.92	2499.85	0.07	28,66	28,91	-0,25	0,0625
Germany	RV 613	31.73	31.64	32.19	3044.08	3043.90	0.17	31,73	31,64	0,09	0,0081
Germany	RV 614	31.24	31.62	31.64	2976.85	2976.75	0.10	31,24	31,62	-0,38	0,1444
Germany	RV 615	27.77	27.60	28.83	2364.10	2363.21	0.89	27,77	27,60	0,17	0,0289
Germany	RV 721	32.03	31.88	32.62	3106.32	3106.01	0.31	32,03	31,88	0,15	0,0225
Germany	RV 724	34.84	34.73	35.10	3652.01	3651.94	0.07	34,84	34,73	0,11	0,0121
Germany	RV 725	34.20	34.30	34.70	3550.22	3550.08	0.14	34,20	34,30	-0,10	0,0100
Germany	RV 726	25.50	25.86	26.30	2010.68	2010.36	0.32	25,50	25,86	-0,36	0,1296
Germany	RV 778	32.96	32.98	33.28	3281.60	3281.54	0.06	32,96	32,98	-0,02	0,0004
Germany	RV 782	30.17	30.09	30.45	2742.84	2742.77	0.07	30,17	30,09	0,08	0,0064
Germany	RV 783	27.30	27.52	27.98	2285.52	2285.28	0.24	27,30	27,52	-0,22	0,0484
Germany	RV 786	34.93	34.63	35.24	3661.20	3661.01	0.19	34,93	34,63	0,30	0,0900
Germany	RV 834	30.49	30.38	30.48	2781.61	2781.61	0.01	30,49	30,38	0,11	0,0121
Germany	RV 870	28.89	28.70	28.74	2484.31	2484.29	0.02	28,89	28,70	0,19	0,0361
Germany	RV 872	33.55	32.78	32.61	3263.54	3263.04	0.50	33,55	32,78	0,77	0,5929
Germany	RV 879	28.27	27.67	28.08	2353.31	2353.12	0.19	28,27	27,67	0,60	0,3600
Germany	RV 884	31.80	31.61	32.08	3039.56	3039.45	0.11	31,80	31,61	0,19	0,0361
Germany	RV 886	29.05	29.13	29.30	2550.95	2550.92	0.03	29,05	29,13	-0,08	0,0064
Germany	RV 890	32.53	32.33	31.99	3126.79	3126.64	0.15	32,53	32,33	0,20	0,0400
Germany	RV 899	32.35	32.36	32.39	3142.80	3142.80	0.00	32,35	32,36	-0,01	0,0001
Germany	RV 901	29.07	28.96	28.72	2508.58	2508.52	0.06	29,07	28,96	0,11	0,0121
Germany	RV 903	31.10	31.24	30.75	2888.71	2888.58	0.13	31,10	31,24	-0,14	0,0196
Germany	RV 905	29.90	29.90	29.95	2685.02	2685.02	0.00	29,90	29,90	0,00	0,0000
Germany	RV 923	29.12	28.85	28.73	2505.71	2505.63	0.08	29,12	28,85	0,27	0,0729
Germany	RV 959	28.95	29.08	29.20	2536.39	2536.36	0.03	28,95	29,08	-0,13	0,0169
Germany	RV 1007	32.21	32.03	32.74	3135.31	3135.04	0.27	32,21	32,03	0,18	0,0324
Germany	RV 1124	29.13	29.45	30.28	2632.74	2632.03	0.70	29,13	29,45	-0,32	0,1024
Germany	RV 1613	31.88	32.29	33.82	3202.77	3200.68	2.09	31,88	32,29	-0,41	0,1681
Germany	RV 1615	32.12	32.10	32.64	3127.47	3127.29	0.19	32,12	32,10	0,02	0,0004
Germany	RV 1616	32.90	32.71	33.52	3275.94	3275.59	0.36	32,90	32,71	0,19	0,0361
Germany	RV 1618	28.63	28.12	28.60	2428.37	2428.21	0.16	28,63	28,12	0,51	0,2601
Germany	RV 1625	30.96	30.58	30.84	2844.76	2844.69	0.08	30,96	30,58	0,38	0,1444

Germany	RV 1630	29.35	29.34	29.87	2614.48	2614.29	0.18	29,35	29,34	0,01	0,0001	
Germany	RV 1633	34.42	34.48	35.27	3617.58	3617.13	0.45	34,42	34,48	-0,06	0,0036	
Germany	RV 1636	31.88	31.94	32.15	3070.12	3070.08	0.04	31,88	31,94	-0,06	0,0036	
Germany	RV 1638	26.50	26.33	26.98	2123.44	2123.21	0.23	26,50	26,33	0,17	0,0289	
Germany	RV 1639	33.62	32.69	32.20	3235.78	3234.74	1.04	33,62	32,69	0,93	0,8649	
Germany	RV 1640	31.15	31.12	31.45	2927.88	2927.81	0.07	31,15	31,12	0,03	0,0009	
Germany	RV 1656	29.94	29.85	30.30	2705.52	2705.40	0.11	29,94	29,85	0,09	0,0081	
Germany	RV 1657	28.10	27.70	28.28	2356.66	2356.48	0.18	28,10	27,70	0,40	0,1600	
Germany	S 158	29.81	29.88	29.89	2674.86	2674.86	0.00	29,81	29,88	-0,07	0,0049	
Germany	S 159	29.07	29.07	29.03	2532.87	2532.87	0.00	29,07	29,07	0,00	0,0000	
Germany	S 162	29.16	29.44	29.07	2562.08	2562.01	0.07	29,16	29,44	-0,28	0,0784	
Germany	S 4541	29.01	28.95	29.00	2520.68	2520.68	0.00	29,01	28,95	0,06	0,0036	
Germany	S 4585	28.41	28.50	28.03	2405.06	2404.93	0.12	28,41	28,50	-0,09	0,0081	
Germany	S 4631	30.97	31.15	31.42	2916.68	2916.58	0.10	30,97	31,15	-0,18	0,0324	
Germany	S 5164	32.52	32.44	32.87	3190.34	3190.24	0.10	32,52	32,44	0,08	0,0064	
Germany	S 5164	29.18	29.11	28.96	2537.55	2537.52	0.03	29,18	29,11	0,07	0,0049	
Greece	RSK 501	30.43	30.42	30.75	2796.92	2796.85	0.07	30,43	30,42	0,01	0,0001	
Greece	RSK 502	29.83	29.04	29.98	2631.95	2631.44	0.51	29,83	29,04	0,79	0,6241	
Greece	RSK 503	29.21	29.51	29.78	2610.91	2610.75	0.16	29,21	29,51	-0,30	0,0900	
Greece	RSK 504	26.20	25.87	25.96	2029.62	2029.56	0.06	26,20	25,87	0,33	0,1089	
Greece	RSK 505	29.01	29.22	29.17	2546.28	2546.25	0.02	29,01	29,22	-0,21	0,0441	
Greece	RSK 506	33.66	33.49	33.79	3396.34	3396.29	0.05	33,66	33,49	0,17	0,0289	
Greece	RV 1119	29.82	29.87	30.33	2701.36	2701.20	0.16	29,82	29,87	-0,05	0,0025	
Greece	RV 1120	30.95	31.06	31.43	2910.47	2910.34	0.13	30,95	31,06	-0,11	0,0121	
Greece	RV 1121	32.91	32.94	32.88	3249.21	3249.20	0.00	32,91	32,94	-0,03	0,0009	
Greece	RV 1122	27.41	27.52	27.54	2267.11	2267.10	0.01	27,41	27,52	-0,11	0,0121	
Greece	RV 1123	29.16	29.44	30.28	2633.90	2633.22	0.68	29,16	29,44	-0,28	0,0784	
Greece	RV 1842	34.51	34.47	34.81	3590.86	3590.79	0.07	34,51	34,47	0,04	0,0016	
Greece	RV 1844	28.39	28.43	28.74	2440.24	2440.17	0.07	28,39	28,43	-0,04	0,0016	
Greece	RV 1845	26.66	27.12	27.72	2214.65	2214.08	0.57	26,66	27,12	-0,46	0,2116	
Greece	RV 1846	29.17	29.04	29.40	2558.57	2558.50	0.07	29,17	29,04	0,13	0,0169	
Greece	RV 1847	28.89	28.85	30.20	2578.99	2577.81	1.18	28,89	28,85	0,04	0,0016	
Greece	RV 1848	33.11	33.07	33.32	3300.12	3300.08	0.04	33,11	33,07	0,04	0,0016	
Mean (all FMB_1/2/M measurements):		30.06		Sum of all $\left[\sum_{i=1}^n M(n)^2 - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n M(n))^2}{n} \right]$:		17.94		Mean (all FMB_1/2 measurements):		29.97	Sum of all Δ^2: 7.1917	
SD (all FMB_1/2/M measurements):		2.34						2.32				
aTEM of FMB				0.30				0.19				
%TEM of FMB				1.01%				0.64%				
R of FMB				0.9833				0.9932				

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.3

2D Intraobserver Error Analysis – Bland-Altman Plots

Supplementary Material, Methods – S3.4

2D Intraobserver Error Analysis – Microsoft Excel Codes for the Calculation of Lin’s Concordance Correlation Coefficient

Tab. S3.4: MS Excel codes and functions to calculate LCCC and its 95CI adapted from www.real-statistics.com (see text or comment below).

Metrics	Microsoft Excel Cell Codes / Functions
Repetition mean of all measurements per repetition (mean)	=MEAN(of all FM_1 and FM_2)
Repetition (sample) variance of all measurements per repetition (var.s)	=VAR.S(of all FM_1 and FM_2)
Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r)	=CORREL(between all FM_1 and FM_2)
LCCC (rc)	=2*r*SQRT(var.s[FM_1+FM_2]/((mean[FM_1-FM_2])^2+ var.s[FM_1]+ var.s[FM_2]))
u ²	=(MEAN[FM_1-FM_2]^2/SQRT(var.s[FM_1*FM_2]))
Sample size (n)	=COUNT(all FM_1)
Fisher transformation of LCCC (rc')	=FISHER(of rc)
a	=(1-r)^2*rc^2/((1-rc^2)*r^2)
b	=2*(1-rc)*rc^3*u^2/((1-rc^2)^2*r)
c	=rc^4*u^2/(2*(1-rc^2)^2*r^2)
Standard error for the fisher transformed LCCC (se)	=SQRT((a+b-c)/(n-2))
Alpha	0.05
Critical value of z (Z-score; z-crit)	=NORM.S.INV(1-ALPHA/2)
Fisher transformed lower 95CI margin of LCCC (lower')	=rc'-z-crit*se
Fisher transformed upper 95CI margin of LCCC (upper')	=rc'+z-crit*se
Lower 95CI margin of LCCC (lower)	=FISHERINV(lower')
Upper 95CI margin of LCCC (upper)	=FISHERINV(upper')
<p>Metrics to calculate LCCC and 95CI are colour-coded for better overview. The FM abbreviation in FM_1 and FM_2 can equally be replaced by FML or FMB. FM indications in [] refer to all FML or FMB values of the repetition set, respectively. The [] are not part of the actual MS Excel code. Codes are adapted from www.real-statistics.com (https://www.real-statistics.com/reliability/interrater-reliability/lins-concordance-correlation-coefficient/). Here, only the =VAR.P() function was replaced by =VAR.S() to translate the LCCC equation from the population formula to its sample counterpart (see text).</p>	

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.5

2D Intraobserver Error Analysis – Calculation Results of Lin’s Concordance Correlation Coefficient for FML and FMB

Tab. S3.5: Results for the calculation of LCCC for FML and FMB. For a graphic representation see figure S3.6a and S3.6b.

LCCC metrics	FML	FMB
Number of measurements (i.e., specimens)	98	98
Number of repetitions per variable	2	2
Total number of repeated measurements	196	196
Mean of repetition 1	35.70	29.99
Mean of repetition 2	35.71	29.96
Sample variance of repetition 1	6.7659	5.4571
Sample variance of repetition 2	6.8961	5.4018
Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r)	0.9969	0.9933
Lin’s concordance correlation coefficient (LCCC)	0.9969	0.9932
Lower 95CI margin	0.9954	0.9898
Upper 95CI margin	0.9979	0.9954
LCCC classification after McBride (2005)	LCCC > 0.99	LCCC > 0.99
LCCC interpretation after McBride (2005)	Almost perfect concordance	Almost perfect concordance
95CI = 95% confidence interval.		

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.6

2D Intraobserver Error Analysis – Graphic Representation of Lin's Concordance Correlation Coefficient for FML and FMB

Figure S3.6a and S3.6b: Scatter plots for all physically measured FML (top) and FMB (bottom) repetitions. Black line = 45-degree reference line, red line = line of best fit (method = lm (linear model)). Pearson's product correlation coefficient r was calculated based on the entire sample. The test statistic outputs (`cor.text()`) for Pearson's r are reported in the plot's subtitles.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.7.1 to S3.7.5

Landmark Precision Error (Centroid Radius Approach), Part 1

Fig. S3.7.1 to S3.7.5 (from top to bottom): Landmark precision error plots showing the relative SD of each repeated landmark per landmark repetition set before (left) and after (right) semilandmark sliding. Blue dotted line = 5% threshold. LM1, 11, 21 and 31 = fixed landmarks.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.7.6 to S3.7.10

Landmark Precision Error (Centroid Radius Approach), Part 2

Fig. S3.7.6 to S3.7.10 (from left to right and from top to bottom): Landmark precision error plots showing the relative SD of each repeated landmark per landmark repetition set before (left) and after (right) semilandmark sliding. Blue dotted line = 5% threshold. LM1, 11, 21 and 31 = fixed landmarks.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.7.11 to S3.7.12

Landmark Precision Error (Centroid Radius Approach), Part 3

Fig. S3.7.11 to S3.7.12 (from top to bottom): Landmark precision error plots showing the relative SD of each repeated landmark per landmark repetition set before (left) and after (right) semilandmark sliding. Blue dotted line = 5% threshold. LM1, 11, 21 and 31 = fixed landmarks.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.8.1 and S3.8.2

3D Landmark Repetition – Error Shape-PCA

Fig. S3.8.1 (top) and S3.8.2 (bottom): Error shape-PCA of the landmark repetitions ($n = 5$, blue points) of a single individual. Pink points = non-repeated individuals from the same population.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.8.3 and S3.8.4

3D Landmark Repetition – Error Shape-PCA

Fig. S3.8.3 (top) and S3.8.4 (bottom): Error shape-PCA of the landmark repetitions ($n = 5$, blue points) of a single individual. Pink points = non-repeated individuals from the same population.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.8.5 and S3.8.6

3D Landmark Repetition – Error Shape-PCA

Fig. S3.8.5 (top) and S3.8.6 (bottom): Error shape-PCA of the landmark repetitions ($n = 5$, blue points) of a single individual. Pink points = non-repeated individuals from the same population.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.8.7 and S3.8.8

3D Landmark Repetition – Error Shape-PCA

Fig. S3.8.7 (top) and S3.8.8 (bottom): Error shape-PCA of the landmark repetitions ($n = 5$, blue points) of a single individual. Pink points = non-repeated individuals from the same population.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.8.9 and S3.8.10

3D Landmark Repetition – Error Shape-PCA

Fig. S3.8.9 (top) and S3.8.10 (bottom): Error shape-PCA of the landmark repetitions ($n = 5$, blue points) of a single individual. Pink points = non-repeated individuals from the same population.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.8.11 and S3.8.12

3D Landmark Repetition – Error Shape-PCA

Fig. S3.8.11 (top) and S3.8.12 (bottom): Error shape-PCA of the landmark repetitions ($n = 5$, blue points) of a single individual. Pink points = non-repeated individuals from the same population.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.9.1 to S3.9.3

Skewness and Kurtosis of FML, FMB and FMI Residual Data, Evaluation of Normality

Tab. S3.9.1: Brief summary statistics of FML residual data to access skewness and kurtosis to check for normality.

Population	Sex	n	Mean	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis
Eritrea	F	7	0	2.93	0.34	-1.93
Eritrea	M	12	0	2.89	-0.19	-0.31
Eritrea	F/M	21	0	2.90	0.05	-0.72
Japan	F	4	0	2.32	0.30	-1.86
Japan	M	4	0	1.06	-0.58	-1.78
Japan	F/M	11	0	1.94	-0.35	-1.35
Germany	F	19	0	2.44	0.23	-1.37
Germany	M	23	0	2.60	-0.12	-1.07
Germany	F/M	49	0	2.46	0.07	-1.13
Greece	F	7	0	2.70	-0.54	-1.24
Greece	M	7	0	3.06	0.13	-1.31
Greece	F/M	17	0	3.04	0.17	-0.35

Tab. S3.9.2: Brief summary statistics of FMB residual data to access skewness and kurtosis to check for normality.

Population	Sex	n	Mean	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis
Eritrea	F	7	0	1.09	-0.40	-1.84
Eritrea	M	12	0	2.90	0.26	-0.19
Eritrea	F/M	21	0	2.36	0.80	1.37
Japan	F	4	0	1.89	-0.61	-1.80
Japan	M	4	0	0.83	-0.36	-2.05
Japan	F/M	11	0	1.92	-0.56	-0.93
Germany	F	19	0	1.98	-0.40	-0.77
Germany	M	23	0	2.12	0.28	-0.66
Germany	F/M	49	0	2.17	0.05	-0.70
Greece	F	7	0	2.21	0.39	-0.45
Greece	M	7	0	2.53	0.57	-0.98
Greece	F/M	17	0	2.38	0.38	-0.91

Tab. S3.9.3: Brief summary statistics of FMI residual data to access skewness and kurtosis to check for normality.

Population	Sex	n	Mean	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis
Eritrea	F	7	0	4.77	-0.35	-1.74
Eritrea	M	12	0	5.61	-1.00	0.08
Eritrea	F/M	21	0	4.99	-0.94	0.47
Japan	F	4	0	4.53	0.36	-1.92
Japan	M	4	0	4.52	0.10	-1.99
Japan	F/M	11	0	3.98	0.67	-1.06
Germany	F	19	0	5.86	0.50	-0.34
Germany	M	23	0	5.40	0.09	-0.84
Germany	F/M	49	0	5.71	0.19	-0.56
Greece	F	7	0	4.73	-0.17	-1.57
Greece	M	7	0	3.75	0.13	-0.93
Greece	F/M	17	0	4.90	0.11	-1.09

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.10.1 to S3.10.4

Intrapopulation, Sex-separated Q-Q Plots for FML Residuals of the Berlin Samples, Evaluation of Normality

Fig. S3.10.1 and S3.10.4 (from left to right and top to bottom): FML residuals Q-Q plots of the sex-known Berlin subsamples. Sex-unknown individuals are not included in any of the intrapopulation Q-Q plots. Coloured area = 95%CI.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.10.5 to S3.10.8

Intrapopulation, Sex-separated Q-Q plots for FMB Residuals of the Berlin Samples, Evaluation of Normality

Fig. S3.10.5 and S3.10.8 (from left to right and top to bottom): FMB residuals Q-Q plots of the sex-known Berlin subsamples. Sex-unknown individuals are not included in any of the intrapopulation Q-Q plots. Coloured area = 95%CI.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.10.9 to S3.10.12

Intrapopulation, Sex-separated Q-Q Plots for FMI Residuals of the Berlin Samples, evaluation of normality

FMI residual Q-Q plot for the sex-known Eritrea subsamples

FMI residual Q-Q plot for the sex-known Japanese subsamples

FMI residual Q-Q plot for the sex-known German subsamples

FMI residual Q-Q plot for the sex-known Greek subsamples

Fig. S3.10.9 and S3.10.12 (from left to right and top to bottom): FMI residuals Q-Q plots of the sex-known Berlin subsamples. Sex-unknown individuals are not included in any of the intrapopulation Q-Q plots. Coloured area = 95%CI.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.11.1 to S3.11.4

Interpopulation, Sex-pooled Q-Q Plots for FML Residuals of the Berlin Samples, Evaluation of Normality

Fig. S3.11.1 and S3.11.4 (from left to right and top to bottom): FML residuals Q-Q plots of the entire Berlin subsamples including the sex-unknown individuals. Grey area = 95%CI.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.11.5 to S3.11.8

Interpopulation, Sex-pooled Q-Q Plots for FMB Residuals of the Berlin Samples, Evaluation of Normality

Fig. S3.11.5 and S3.11.8 (from left to right and top to bottom): FMB residuals Q-Q plots of the entire Berlin subsamples including the sex-unknown individuals. Grey area = 95%CI.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.11.9 to S3.11.12

Interpopulation, Sex-pooled Q-Q Plots for FMI Residuals of the Berlin Samples, Evaluation of Normality

Fig. S3.11.9 and S3.11.12 (from left to right and top to bottom): FMI residuals Q-Q plots of the entire Berlin subsamples including the sex-unknown individuals. Grey area = 95%CI.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.12.1 to S3.12.4

Intrapopulation, Sex-separated Histograms for FML Residuals of the Berlin Samples, Evaluation of Normality

Fig. S3.12.1 and S3.12.4 (from left to right and top to bottom): FML residuals histograms of the of the sex-known Berlin subsamples. Sex-unknown individuals are not included. Curve line = density probability.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.12.5 to S3.12.8

Intrapopulation, Sex-separated Histograms for FMB Residuals of the Berlin Samples, Evaluation of Normality

Fig. S3.12.5 and S3.12.8 (from left to right and top to bottom): FMB residuals histograms of the of the sex-known Berlin subsamples. Sex-unknown individuals are not included. Curve line = density probability.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.12.9 to S3.12.12

Intrapopulation, Sex-separated Histograms for FMI Residuals of the Berlin Samples, Evaluation of Normality

Fig. S3.12.9 and S3.12.12 (from left to right and top to bottom): FMI residuals histograms of the of the sex-known Berlin subsamples. Sex-unknown individuals are not included. Curve line = density probability.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.13.1 to S3.13.4

Interpopulation, Sex-pooled Histograms for FML Residuals of the Berlin Samples, Evaluation of Normality

Fig. S3.13.1 and S3.13.4 (from left to right and top to bottom): FML residuals histograms of the of the entire Berlin subsamples including the sex-unknown individuals. Curve line = density probability.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.13.5 to S3.13.8

Interpopulation, Sex-pooled Histograms for FMB Residuals of the Berlin Samples, Evaluation of Normality

Fig. S3.13.5 and S3.13.8 (from left to right and top to bottom): FMB residuals histograms of the of the entire Berlin subsamples including the sex-unknown individuals. Curve line = density probability.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.13.9 to S3.13.12

Interpopulation, Sex-pooled Histograms for FMI Residuals of the Berlin Samples, Evaluation of Normality

Fig. S3.13.9 and S3.13.12 (from left to right and top to bottom): FMI residuals histograms of the of the entire Berlin subsamples including the sex-unknown individuals. Curve line = density probability.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.14

Shapiro Wilk Test of Normality of the 2D FM Variable Residuals

Tab. S3.14: Results of the Shapiro-Wilk test of normality of all 2D FM variable residuals (FMI, FMB and FMI).

Population	Variable	Sample	n	W	p-value	Alpha (α)	Result
Eritrea	FML	F/M	21	0.94744	0.30440	0.05	p > 0.05
Eritrea	FML	F	7	0.84639	0.11390	0.05	p > 0.05
Eritrea	FML	M	12	0.94335	0.54260	0.05	p > 0.05
Eritrea	FMB	F/M	21	0.92098	0.09078	0.05	p > 0.05
Eritrea	FMB	F	7	0.84676	0.11480	0.05	p > 0.05
Eritrea	FMB	M	12	0.93721	0.46270	0.05	p > 0.05
Eritrea	FMI	F/M	21	0.91172	0.05939	0.05	p > 0.05
Eritrea	FMI	F	7	0.88721	0.26040	0.05	p > 0.05
Eritrea	FMI	M	12	0.88930	0.11540	0.05	p > 0.05
Japan	FML	F/M	11	0.93609	0.47570	0.05	p > 0.05
Japan	FML	F	4	0.96566	0.81440	0.05	p > 0.05
Japan	FML	M	4	0.86261	0.26970	0.05	p > 0.05
Japan	FMB	F/M	11	0.90362	0.20460	0.05	p > 0.05
Japan	FMB	F	4	0.83546	0.18250	0.05	p > 0.05
Japan	FMB	M	4	0.87409	0.31400	0.05	p > 0.05
Japan	FMI	F/M	11	0.88208	0.11060	0.05	p > 0.05
Japan	FMI	F	4	0.95356	0.73840	0.05	p > 0.05
Japan	FMI	M	4	0.99662	0.98830	0.05	p > 0.05
Germany	FML	F/M	49	0.95865	0.08335	0.05	p > 0.05
Germany	FML	F	19	0.93341	0.20010	0.05	p > 0.05
Germany	FML	M	23	0.94610	0.24240	0.05	p > 0.05
Germany	FMB	F/M	49	0.97746	0.46400	0.05	p > 0.05
Germany	FMB	F	19	0.94093	0.27400	0.05	p > 0.05
Germany	FMB	M	23	0.96367	0.54120	0.05	p > 0.05
Germany	FMI	F/M	49	0.98905	0.92620	0.05	p > 0.05
Germany	FMI	F	19	0.95356	0.73840	0.05	p > 0.05
Germany	FMI	M	23	0.99662	0.98830	0.05	p > 0.05
Greece	FML	F/M	17	0.96158	0.66140	0.05	p > 0.05
Greece	FML	F	7	0.93752	0.61650	0.05	p > 0.05
Greece	FML	M	7	0.95998	0.81850	0.05	p > 0.05
Greece	FMB	F/M	17	0.94230	0.34650	0.05	p > 0.05
Greece	FMB	F	7	0.86609	0.17150	0.05	p > 0.05
Greece	FMB	M	7	0.93512	0.59520	0.05	p > 0.05
Greece	FMI	F/M	17	0.96912	0.80290	0.05	p > 0.05
Greece	FMI	F	7	0.97094	0.90510	0.05	p > 0.05
Greece	FMI	M	7	0.97251	0.91590	0.05	p > 0.05

N = sample size, F = female, M = male, F/M = sex-pooled sample, including sex-indeterminable individuals. Green cell = non-significant p-value > 0.05 suggesting normal distribution.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.15 and S3.16

Levene’s Test of Homogeneity of Variances of the 2D FM Variable Residuals between Compared Sample Groups

Tab. S3.15: Results of the Levene’s test of Variance Homogeneity of all 2D FM variable residuals (FML, FMB and FMI).

Population	Sample	Variable	Center	DF1	DF2	F-value	p-value, PR (>F)	Result
All populations	Sex-seperated, no ind.	FML	Median	7	75	0.4980	0.8332	p > 0.05
All populations	Sex-seperated, no ind.	FMB	Median	7	75	0.8937	0.5159	p > 0.05
All populations	Sex-seperated, no ind.	FMI	Median	7	75	0.3338	0.9361	p > 0.05
All populations	Sex-pooled, with ind.	FML	Median	3	94	0.6073	0.6119	p > 0.05
All populations	Sex-pooled, with ind.	FMB	Median	3	94	0.3856	0.7636	p > 0.05
All populations	Sex-pooled, with ind.	FMI	Median	3	94	0.9851	0.4033	p > 0.05

Descriptive Summary Statistics – FML

Tab. S3.16: Descriptive summary statistics for FML (foramen magnum length).

Group	Sex	n	Min	Max	Range	Mean	SD	Median	SE	95%CI (Lower)	95%CI (Upper)	Skewness	Kurtosis
Eritrea	F	7	31.00	37.85	6.85	33.92	2.93	32.48	1.11	31.21	36.63	0.34	-1.93
Eritrea	M	12	30.73	41.87	11.14	36.27	2.89	36.75	0.83	34.44	38.11	-0.19	-0.32
Eritrea	ind	2	34.70	35.07	0.37	34.89	0.26	34.89	0.18	32.53	37.24	0.00	-2.75
Eritrea	F/M	21	30.73	41.87	11.14	35.36	2.90	35.75	0.63	34.04	36.68	0.05	-0.72
Japan	F	4	31.52	37.06	5.54	33.96	2.32	33.62	1.16	30.27	37.65	0.30	-1.89
Japan	M	4	35.02	37.46	2.44	36.55	1.06	36.87	0.53	34.86	38.24	-0.58	-1.78
Japan	ind	3	33.00	35.57	2.57	34.59	1.39	35.20	0.80	31.14	38.04	-0.35	-2.33
Japan	F/M	11	31.52	37.46	5.94	35.07	1.94	35.20	0.59	33.77	36.38	-0.35	-1.35
Germany	F	19	32.38	39.65	7.27	35.69	2.44	35.05	0.56	34.52	36.87	0.23	-1.37
Germany	M	23	30.94	40.17	9.23	36.52	2.60	36.45	0.54	35.39	37.64	-0.12	-1.07
Germany	ind	7	32.94	38.81	5.87	35.87	2.18	34.94	0.82	33.85	37.88	0.10	-1.83
Germany	F/M	49	30.94	40.17	9.23	36.11	2.46	35.59	0.35	35.40	36.81	0.07	-1.13
Greece	F	7	30.26	38.11	7.85	35.04	2.70	35.65	1.02	32.54	37.54	-0.57	-1.24
Greece	M	7	30.61	39.76	9.15	34.76	3.06	34.99	1.15	31.93	37.58	0.13	-1.31
Greece	ind	3	35.25	42.03	6.78	37.72	3.75	35.87	2.16	28.41	47.03	0.37	-2.33
Greece	F/M	17	30.26	42.03	11.77	35.40	3.04	35.65	0.74	33.83	36.96	0.17	-0.35

All measurements are in millimetre (mm). n = number of individuals, Min = minimum value, Max = maximum value, SD = standard deviation, SE = standard error of the mean, 95%CI = 95% confidence interval of the mean. F = females, M = males, ind = indeterminable, F/M = sex-pooled sample including sex-unknown individuals.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.17
Descriptive Summary Statistics – FMB

Tab. S3.17: Descriptive summary statistics for FMB (foramen magnum breadth).

Group	Sex	n	Min	Max	Range	Mean	SD	Median	SE	95%CI (Lower)	95%CI (Upper)	Skewness	Kurtosis
Eritrea	F	7	25.99	28.68	2.69	27.65	1.09	28.35	0.41	26.65	28.66	-0.40	-1.84
Eritrea	M	12	24.50	35.39	10.89	29.16	2.90	28.93	0.84	27.31	31.00	0.26	-0.20
Eritrea	ind	2	27.25	28.64	1.39	27.94	0.98	27.94	0.70	19.11	36.78	0.00	-2.75
Eritrea	F/M	21	24.50	35.39	10.89	28.54	2.36	28.52	0.52	27.47	29.61	0.80	1.37
Japan	F	4	26.75	30.89	4.14	29.48	1.89	30.14	0.94	26.48	32.48	-0.61	-1.80
Japan	M	4	30.78	32.54	1.76	31.88	0.83	32.10	0.41	30.56	33.20	-0.36	-2.05
Japan	ind	3	26.97	30.01	3.04	28.85	1.64	29.57	0.95	24.77	32.93	-0.35	-2.33
Japan	F/M	11	26.75	32.54	5.79	30.18	1.92	30.56	0.58	28.89	31.47	-0.56	-0.93
Germany	F	19	25.68	32.97	7.29	30.25	1.98	30.13	0.45	29.29	31.20	-0.41	-0.77
Germany	M	23	26.42	34.79	8.37	30.39	2.12	29.85	0.44	29.47	31.31	0.28	-0.66
Germany	ind	7	27.69	34.78	7.09	31.91	2.61	33.16	0.99	29.50	34.33	-0.37	-1.64
Germany	F/M	49	25.68	34.79	9.11	30.55	2.17	30.44	0.31	29.93	31.17	0.05	-0.70
Greece	F	7	26.04	33.58	7.54	29.46	2.21	29.30	0.84	27.41	31.50	0.40	-0.45
Greece	M	7	26.89	34.49	7.60	29.82	2.53	29.36	0.96	27.48	32.16	0.57	-0.97
Greece	ind	3	28.41	33.09	4.68	31.48	2.66	32.93	1.53	24.88	38.08	-0.38	-2.33
Greece	F/M	17	26.04	34.49	8.45	29.96	2.38	29.36	0.58	28.74	31.19	0.37	-0.91

All measurements are in millimetre (mm). n = number of individuals, Min = minimum value, Max = maximum value, SD = standard deviation, SE = standard error of the mean, 95%CI = 95% confidence interval of the mean. F = females, M = males, ind = indeterminable, F/M = sex-pooled sample including sex-unknown individuals.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.18
Descriptive Summary Statistics – FMI

Tab. S3.18: Descriptive summary statistics for FMI (foramen magnum index).

Group	Sex	n	Min	Max	Range	Mean	SD	Median	SE	95%CI (Lower)	95%CI (Upper)	Skewness	Kurtosis
Eritrea	F	7	75.36	87.3	11.94	81.85	4.77	83.41	1.80	77.44	86.26	-0.35	-1.74
Eritrea	M	12	67.02	86.81	19.79	80.44	5.61	82.18	1.62	76.88	84.00	-1.00	0.08
Eritrea	ind	2	78.54	81.65	3.11	80.10	2.20	80.10	1.56	60.34	99.85	0.00	-2.75
Eritrea	F/M	21	67.02	87.30	20.28	80.88	4.99	81.83	1.09	78.61	83.15	-0.94	0.47
Japan	F	4	82.47	93.04	10.57	86.91	4.53	86.07	2.27	79.70	94.13	0.36	-1.92
Japan	M	4	82.15	92.90	10.75	87.30	4.52	87.07	2.26	80.10	94.49	0.10	-1.97
Japan	ind	3	81.71	84.35	2.64	83.36	1.44	84.01	0.83	79.79	86.92	-0.36	-2.33
Japan	F/M	11	81.71	93.04	11.33	86.08	3.98	84.85	1.20	83.41	88.75	0.67	-1.06
Germany	F	19	74.06	98.15	24.09	84.94	5.86	83.80	1.34	82.11	87.76	0.50	-0.33
Germany	M	23	72.69	94.53	21.84	83.40	5.40	82.54	1.13	81.06	85.73	0.10	-0.85
Germany	ind	7	80.88	95.16	14.28	88.97	4.82	89.62	1.82	84.51	93.42	-0.35	-1.38
Germany	F/M	49	72.69	98.15	25.46	84.79	5.71	84.16	0.82	83.15	86.43	0.19	-0.56
Greece	F	7	76.89	90.66	13.77	84.20	4.73	85.77	1.80	79.82	88.58	-0.17	-1.57
Greece	M	7	80.00	92.24	12.24	85.90	3.75	85.47	1.42	82.44	89.37	0.13	-0.94
Greece	ind	3	78.35	93.87	15.52	83.81	8.72	79.21	5.04	62.14	105.48	0.38	-2.33
Greece	F/M	17	76.89	93.87	16.98	84.83	4.91	85.47	1.19	82.31	87.36	0.11	-1.09

All measurements are in millimetre (mm). n = number of individuals, Min = minimum value, Max = maximum value, SD = standard deviation, SE = standard error of the mean, 95%CI = 95% confidence interval of the mean. F = females, M = males, ind = indeterminable, F/M = sex-pooled sample including sex-unknown individuals.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.19

Summary Statistics from the Published Literature

Tab. S3.19: Overview of the collected summary statistics of FML, FMB and FMI from various osteometric FM studies (n = 81) not including the new berlin samples. n = number of individuals per sex group/population, ±SD = standard deviation from mean, Min = minimum value, Max = maximum value.

	Study	Population	Method	Sex	n	FML				FMB				FMI			
						Mean	±SD	Min	Max	Mean	±SD	Min	Max	Mean	±SD	Min	Max
Africa	Zdilla et al. (2017)	Africa	Dry*	F/M	8	39.27	2.97	33.83	42.66	32.78	4.16	29.69	42.17	83.47	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Rehab et al. (2015)	Egypt	CT	F	24	38.75	3.52	33.00	45.00	31.38	2.08	28.00	35.00	80.98	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Rehab et al. (2015)	Egypt	CT	M	46	42.17	3.78	3.40	51.00	33.98	3.43	25.00	44.00	80.58	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Darwish et al. (2014)	Egypt	CT	F	45	30.28	0.25	22.00	40.00	27.10	2.40	16.00	32.00	89.50	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Darwish et al. (2014)	Egypt	CT	M	55	35.30	1.90	31.00	40.00	30.00	1.90	25.00	34.00	84.99	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Abo El-Atta et al. (2020)	Egypt	CT	F	204	35.70	3.30	28.20	46.90	29.90	2.70	24.50	38.50	83.75*	9.38	82.09	86.88
	Abo El-Atta et al. (2020)	Egypt	CT	M	163	36.80	3.30	25.50	51.90	31.50	2.60	22.50	38.50	85.60*	10.35	74.18	88.24
	Saleh et al. (2019)	Egypt	CT	F	50	33.53	3.16	N/A	N/A	28.12	1.95	N/A	N/A	83.87	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Saleh et al. (2019)	Egypt	CT	M	50	37.11	3.38	N/A	N/A	30.34	2.86	N/A	N/A	81.76	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Sheta et al. (2015)	Egypt	Dry	F	50	27.80	3.10	22.30	35.10	23.50	3.00	20.00	30.30	84.53	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Sheta et al. (2015)	Egypt	Dry	M	50	33.70	3.70	22.30	38.20	28.10	1.80	21.50	30.00	83.38	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Loyal et al. (2013)	Kenya	Dry	F/M	202	38.50	6.50	N/A	N/A	35.00	7.00	N/A	N/A	90.91	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Osunwoke and Oladipo (2012)	Nigeria	Dry	F/M	120	36.11	2.60	N/A	N/A	29.56	2.60	N/A	N/A	81.86	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Ukoha et al. (2011)	Nigeria	Dry	F	10	34.39	3.88	N/A	N/A	28.16	1.99	N/A	N/A	81.88	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Ukoha et al. (2011)	Nigeria	Dry	M	90	36.26	2.39	N/A	N/A	30.09	2.58	N/A	N/A	82.98	N/A	N/A	N/A
Ibrahim (2019)	Sudan	CT	F	28	36.13	2.72	N/A	N/A	30.29	2.92	N/A	N/A	83.84	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Ibrahim (2019)	Sudan	CT	M	72	37.60	3.01	N/A	N/A	30.84	2.67	N/A	N/A	82.02	N/A	N/A	N/A	
NA	Berge and Bergman (2001)	USA	Dry	F/M	100	33.80	N/A	24.00	41.00	28.30	N/A	23.00	53.00	83.73	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Wanebo and Chicoine (2001)	USA	Dry	F/M	32	36.00	3.00	30.00	36.00	31.00	2.00	25.00	33.00	86.11	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Wanebo and Chicoine (2001)	USA	CT	F/M	6	36.00	2.00	34.00	38.00	32.00	2.00	29.00	35.00	88.89	N/A	N/A	N/A
South America (SA)	Damiani et al. (2012)	Brazil	MRI	F/M	40	34.78	2.19	28.44	39.97	28.69	2.73	21.34	34.60	82.49	N/A	N/A	N/A
	de Lucena et al. (2019)	Brazil	Dry	F	71	33.91	3.19	22.08	41.17	28.91	2.83	20.37	36.32	86.74*	8.61	67.92	123.98
	de Lucena et al. (2019)	Brazil	Dry	M	88	35.01	3.03	29.16	43.81	30.12	2.95	22.63	37.84	85.36*	10.82	46.00	132.60
	Lopez-Capp et al. (2018)	Brazil	Dry	F	47	30.79	3.30	25.30	39.53	32.09	3.04	25.23	37.99	104.22	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Lopez-Capp et al. (2018)	Brazil	Dry	M	53	32.36	3.26	26.24	41.31	33.70	3.62	25.12	41.75	104.14	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Pires et al. (2016)	Brazil	Dry	F/M	77	34.23	2.54	26.90	39.72	28.62	2.83	22.67	36.01	83.61	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Suazo et al. (2009)	Brazil	Dry	F	71	35.60	2.50	N/A	N/A	29.5	1.90	N/A	N/A	82.87	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Suazo et al. (2009)	Brazil	Dry	M	144	36.50	2.60	N/A	N/A	30.6	2.50	N/A	N/A	83.84	N/A	N/A	N/A
Espinoza et al. (2011)	Chile	CT	F	50	35.60	3.00	N/A	N/A	30.10	2.40	N/A	N/A	84.55	N/A	N/A	N/A	

	Espinoza et al. (2011)	Chile	CT	M	50	37.40	3.30	N/A	N/A	31.90	2.60	N/A	N/A	85.29	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Zdilla et al. (2017)	Peru	Dry*	F/M	59	35.43	3.25	28.8	43.46	32.28	2.80	27.53	39.17	91.11	N/A	N/A	N/A
Asia	Zdilla et al. (2017)	Bengal	Dry*	F/M	15	39.09	2.62	35.37	43.63	32.99	2.11	30.52	36.29	84.39	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Song et al. (1992)	China	Dry	F	30	32.10	2.10	N/A	N/A	25.80	1.80	N/A	N/A	80.37	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Song et al. (1992)	China	Dry	M	30	34.10	2.60	N/A	N/A	27.50	2.40	N/A	N/A	80.65	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Zdilla et al. (2017)	East Asia	Dry*	F/M	7	38.38	2.04	34.60	41.01	33.53	2.72	29.56	36.81	87.36	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Ashwini and Khona (2018)	India	Dry	F/M	162	33.70	1.40	31.00	36.00	27.00	1.60	25.00	30.00	80.12	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Raghavendra Babu et al. (2012)	India	Dry	F	40	32.57	2.08	29.70	37.70	28.19	1.76	24.70	32.80	86.55	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Raghavendra Babu et al. (2012)	India	Dry	M	50	35.68	1.77	30.50	38.90	28.91	1.62	24.10	32.50	81.03	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Chandekar and Jiwane (2017)	India	Dry	F	34	31.50	1.88	N/A	N/A	27.41	1.42	N/A	N/A	87.02	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Chandekar and Jiwane (2017)	India	Dry	M	46	36.23	1.76	N/A	N/A	29.06	2.54	N/A	N/A	80.21	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Chethan et al. (2012)	India	Dry	F/M	53	31.00	2.40	N/A	N/A	25.20	2.40	N/A	N/A	81.29	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Devadas et al. (2017)	India	Dry	F	43	32.10	N/A	N/A	N/A	26.10	N/A	N/A	N/A	81.31	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Devadas et al. (2017)	India	Dry	M	57	36.70	N/A	N/A	N/A	29.70	N/A	N/A	N/A	80.93	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Fathima and Babu (2016)	India	Dry	F/M	53	38.00	N/A	23.00	53.00	35.00	N/A	20.00	52.00	92.11	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Jain et al. (2013)	India	Dry	F	30	32.90	3.00	N/A	N/A	29.50	2.80	N/A	N/A	89.67	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Jain et al. (2013)	India	Dry	M	38	36.90	2.00	N/A	N/A	31.50	2.70	N/A	N/A	85.37	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Kanchan et al. (2013)	India	Dry	F	49	33.60	2.63	27.00	39.00	26.74	2.36	22.00	31.00	79.58	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Kanchan et al. (2013)	India	Dry	M	69	34.51	2.77	27.00	41.00	27.36	2.09	23.00	32.00	79.28	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Kamath et al. (2015)	India	Dry	F	31	30.99	3.49	24.41	42.46	25.45	2.31	20.22	30.71	82.12	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Kamath et al. (2015)	India	Dry	M	41	33.21	2.52	26.09	42.87	26.92	2.52	21.69	34.08	81.06	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Kanodia et al. (2012)	India	Dry	F	36	31.90	3.30	N/A	N/A	26.60	0.35	N/A	N/A	83.39	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Kanodia et al. (2012)	India	Dry	M	64	33.80	3.40	N/A	N/A	28.20	2.60	N/A	N/A	83.43	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Kumar et al. (2019)	India	CT	F	50	32.64	1.80	N/A	N/A	26.73	2.50	N/A	N/A	81.89	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Kumar et al. (2019)	India	CT	M	50	34.95	2.42	N/A	N/A	28.64	2.21	N/A	N/A	81.95	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Mishra et al. (2018)	India	Dry	F/M	71	34.09	2.23	30.22	40.90	28.22	2.19	22.67	33.36	82.78	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Petkar et al. (2017)	India	Dry	F	50	33.64	2.24	29.00	38.00	27.56	2.20	N/A	N/A	81.93	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Petkar et al. (2017)	India	Dry	M	58	34.34	2.89	26.00	41.00	28.59	2.18	N/A	N/A	83.26	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Muthukumar et al. (2005)	India	Dry	F/M	50	33.30	N/A	27.00	39.00	27.90	N/A	23.00	32.00	83.78	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Patil and Kumar (2019)	India	Dry	F/M	105	37.65	N/A	N/A	N/A	32.44	N/A	N/A	N/A	88.68*	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Radhika (2012)	India	Dry	F/M	150	35.30	2.71	27.00	43.00	29.49	2.57	24.00	35.00	83.54	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Radhakrishnan et al. (2012)	India	Dry	F	45	31.72	2.14	N/A	N/A	26.59	1.64	N/A	N/A	83.83	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Radhakrishnan et al. (2012)	India	Dry	M	55	34.04	2.36	N/A	N/A	28.63	1.89	N/A	N/A	84.11	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Raikar et al. (2016)	India	Radio	F	75	32.49	3.17	N/A	N/A	29.66	2.71	N/A	N/A	91.29	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Raikar et al. (2016)	India	Radio	M	75	34.19	3.57	N/A	N/A	31.77	3.59	N/A	N/A	92.92	N/A	N/A	N/A
Rajkumar et al. (2017)	India	Dry	F/M	298	33.98	2.75	N/A	N/A	28.16	2.15	N/A	N/A	83.14*	6.33	N/A	N/A	
Remya et al. (2017)	India	Dry	F/M	50	33.64	2.28	30.00	37.00	27.04	2.14	22.00	32.00	80.38	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Revankar et al. (2020)	India	Dry	F/M	40	34.36	3.13	27.00	38.87	28.48	3.97	16.09	38.11	82.89	N/A	N/A	N/A	

Routal et al. (1984)	India	Dry	F	37	29.60	1.90	N/A	N/A	27.10	1.60	N/A	N/A	91.55	N/A	N/A	N/A
Routal et al. (1984)	India	Dry	M	104	35.50	2.80	N/A	N/A	32.00	2.80	N/A	N/A	90.14	N/A	N/A	N/A
Saini et al. (2014)	India	Dry	F	48	33.03	1.88	N/A	N/A	27.75	1.68	N/A	N/A	84.01	N/A	N/A	N/A
Saini et al. (2014)	India	Dry	M	110	34.24	2.31	N/A	N/A	28.99	1.77	N/A	N/A	84.67	N/A	N/A	N/A
Saini et al. (2014)	India	Dry	F	119	32.89	2.31	N/A	N/A	27.15	2.20	N/A	N/A	82.55	N/A	N/A	N/A
Saini et al. (2014)	India	Dry	M	206	34.30	2.52	N/A	N/A	28.43	2.05	N/A	N/A	82.89	N/A	N/A	N/A
Sampada et al. (2017)	India	Dry	F/M	100	34.84	N/A	N/A	N/A	29.39	N/A	N/A	N/A	84.36	N/A	N/A	N/A
Sharma and Mehra (2018)	India	Dry	F/M	75	35.11	3.12	27.01	43.14	29.35	3.48	25.49	38.11	83.59	N/A	N/A	N/A
(Sharma et al., 2015)	India	Dry	F/M	50	38.76	N/A	N/A	N/A	33.44	N/A	N/A	N/A	86.27	N/A	N/A	N/A
Sharma et al. (2020)	India	Dry	F/M	62	34.17	N/A	N/A	N/A	28.86	N/A	N/A	N/A	84.46	N/A	N/A	N/A
Shepur et al. (2014)	India	CT	F	15	35.20	3.10	30.00	39.00	27.60	2.30	24.00	33.00	78.41	N/A	N/A	N/A
Shepur et al. (2014)	India	CT	M	15	38.50	3.60	32.00	45.00	29.10	2.30	25.00	33.00	75.58	N/A	N/A	N/A
Singh et al. (2019)	India	Dry	F/M	120	33.79	2.60	30.05	40.07	28.25	1.83	24.25	32.32	83.91*	6.43	71.88	97.94
Singh et al. (2019)	India	Dry	F/M	84	33.57	2.82	29.20	39.10	27.49	2.61	21.11	31.80	82.09*	7.04	69.79	93.53
Singh and Talwar (2013)	India	Dry	F	24	32.31	3.24	N/A	N/A	27.21	2.99	N/A	N/A	84.22	N/A	N/A	N/A
Singh and Talwar (2013)	India	Dry	M	26	33.54	2.80	N/A	N/A	27.77	2.10	N/A	N/A	82.80	N/A	N/A	N/A
Van Vliet et al. (2019)	India	CT	F	73	35.58	2.80	30.40	41.30	30.37	2.90	25.20	39.50	85.36	N/A	N/A	N/A
Van Vliet et al. (2019)	India	CT	M	77	38.02	2.80	31.10	46.30	31.85	2.95	24.60	39.30	83.77	N/A	N/A	N/A
Tambawala et al. (2016)	India	CT	F	115	34.46	2.38	28.25	38.60	29.16	2.53	23.30	35.85	84.62	N/A	N/A	N/A
Tambawala et al. (2016)	India	CT	M	111	36.22	2.33	31.25	42.70	30.80	2.51	24.70	40.20	85.04	N/A	N/A	N/A
Veeramani et al. (2018)	India	Dry	F	19	35.00	N/A	N/A	N/A	32.00	N/A	N/A	N/A	91.43	N/A	N/A	N/A
Veeramani et al. (2018)	India	Dry	M	81	37.00	N/A	N/A	N/A	33.00	N/A	N/A	N/A	89.19	N/A	N/A	N/A
Vinutha et al. (2018)	India	CT	F	90	33.83	3.51	24.70	41.40	27.98	2.53	23.00	34.30	82.71	N/A	N/A	N/A
Vinutha et al. (2018)	India	CT	M	110	35.96	3.75	28.30	45.60	30.38	2.84	23.30	40.30	84.48	N/A	N/A	N/A
Yadav and Goswami (2014)	India	Dry	F	46	33.11	2.03	N/A	N/A	26.71	1.76	N/A	N/A	80.67	N/A	N/A	N/A
Yadav and Goswami (2014)	India	Dry	M	50	35.22	2.17	N/A	N/A	27.60	2.26	N/A	N/A	78.36	N/A	N/A	N/A
Aghakhani et al. (2016)	Iran	CT	F	50	34.38	1.47	N/A	N/A	28.34	1.43	N/A	N/A	82.45*	7.36	N/A	N/A
Aghakhani et al. (2016)	Iran	CT	M	50	37.72	1.01	N/A	N/A	31.68	1.3	N/A	N/A	83.97*	13.24	N/A	N/A
Uthman et al. (2012)	Iraq	CT	F	45	32.9	2.00	26.90	38.00	27.30	2.20	22.30	31.80	82.98	N/A	N/A	N/A
Uthman et al. (2012)	Iraq	CT	M	43	34.90	2.00	29.30	40.80	29.50	2.50	24.00	34.80	84.53	N/A	N/A	N/A
Zdilla et al. (2017)	Malaysia	Dry*	F/M	15	38.59	2.80	33.60	41.75	33.31	2.37	29.59	36.81	86.32	N/A	N/A	N/A
Maharjan et al. (2018)	Nepal	Dry	F	43	30.70	2.28	N/A	N/A	25.19	2.03	N/A	N/A	82.05	N/A	N/A	N/A
Maharjan et al. (2018)	Nepal	Dry	M	53	33.45	2.25	N/A	N/A	27.64	2.02	N/A	N/A	82.63	N/A	N/A	N/A
Kumar et al. (2015)	Oman	Dry	F	17	33.22	2.00	29.5	34.75	29.49	1.66	26.00	31.75	88.77	N/A	N/A	N/A
Kumar et al. (2015)	Oman	Dry	M	19	36.78	1.52	35.00	39.75	30.05	2.36	25.75	34.25	81.70	N/A	N/A	N/A
Madadin et al. (2017)	Saudi Arabia	CT	F	100	36.10	2.65	31.00	47.00	30.60	2.47	26.00	43.00	84.96*	6.39	71.79	107.89
Madadin et al. (2017)	Saudi Arabia	CT	M	100	37.21	2.15	31.00	41.00	31.56	2.25	25.00	36.00	85.22*	6.35	68.29	100.00
Akay et al. (2017)	Turkey	CT	F	102	34.66	2.31	27.20	41.60	29.78	2.05	25.60	35.60	85.92	N/A	N/A	N/A
Akay et al. (2017)	Turkey	CT	M	88	36.43	2.32	31.20	40.40	31.26	2.41	26.40	38.80	85.81	N/A	N/A	N/A
Avci et al. (2011)	Turkey	Dry	F/M	30	34.50	N/A	N/A	N/A	29.00	N/A	N/A	N/A	84.06	N/A	N/A	N/A

	Cirpan et al. (2016)	Turkey	Dry	F/M	150	34.38	2.38	29.00	43.60	28.95	24.20	35.00	2.19	84.21	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Erdil et al. (2010)	Turkey	CT	F	29	34.41	3.89	N/A	N/A	29.98	2.78	N/A	N/A	84.94*	7.67	N/A	N/A	
	Erdil et al. (2010)	Turkey	CT	M	25	36.95	4.01	N/A	N/A	30.75	2.81	N/A	N/A	83.70*	9.27	N/A	N/A	
	Göçmez et al. (2014)	Turkey	CT	F	56	34.26	3.95	N/A	N/A	28.71	2.38	N/A	N/A	83.80	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Göçmez et al. (2014)	Turkey	CT	M	44	35.38	3.10	N/A	N/A	30.57	2.3	N/A	N/A	86.40	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Govsa et al. (2011)	Turkey	Dry	F/M	144	37.20	3.50	27.00	45.00	30.80	2.90	21.20	36.90	82.80	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	İlgüy et al. (2014)	Turkey	CT	F	95	35.62	2.43	N/A	N/A	31.09	2.36	N/A	N/A	87.28	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	İlgüy et al. (2014)	Turkey	CT	M	66	37.79	2.25	N/A	N/A	32.69	2.29	N/A	N/A	86.50	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	İlhan et al. (2017)	Turkey	Dry	F/M	100	35.18	2.94	28.01	43.44	29.73	2.54	20.86	35.65	84.51	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Kizilkanat et al. (2006)	Turkey	Dry	F/M	59	34.80	2.20	29.70	39.70	29.60	2.40	24.40	38.60	85.06	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Murshed et al. (2003)	Turkey	CT	F	53	34.60	3.16	28.00	42.00	29.30	2.19	24,00	33,00	84.68	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Murshed et al. (2003)	Turkey	CT	M	57	37.20	3.43	31.00	45.00	31.60	2.99	27,00	40,00	84.95	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Sendemir et al. (1994)	Turkey	Dry	F/M	38	35.60	2.30	N/A	N/A	29.90	2.10	N/A	N/A	83.99	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Sendemir et al. (1994)	Turkey	Dry	F/M	27	35.10	2.80	N/A	N/A	28.70	2.20	N/A	N/A	81.77	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Sendemir et al. (1994)	Turkey	CT	F/M	23	36.40	2.80	N/A	N/A	30.00	1.40	N/A	N/A	82.42	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Tellioglu et al. (2018)	Turkey	CT	F	50	32.99	2.65	N/A	N/A	28.40	2.72	N/A	N/A	86.09	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Tellioglu et al. (2018)	Turkey	CT	M	50	34.73	2.21	N/A	N/A	30.47	2.25	N/A	N/A	87.73	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Europe	Zdilla et al. (2017)	Europe	Dry*	F/M	17	38.55	3.91	31.35	45.42	33.27	3.70	26.56	40.54	86.30	N/A	N/A	N/A
		Gapert et al. (2009b)	Britain	Dry	F	82	34.71	1.91	29.83	39.94	29.36	1.96	25.27	36.25	84.59	N/A	N/A	N/A
		Gapert et al. (2009b)	Britain	Dry	M	76	35.91	2.41	30.81	42.68	30.51	1.77	24.85	35.04	84.96	N/A	N/A	N/A
		Gapert et al. (2013)	Britain	Dry	F	66	34.78	1.97	30.81	41.53	29.35	2.06	25.27	36.25	84.39	N/A	N/A	N/A
		Gapert et al. (2013)	Britain	Dry	M	69	35.79	2.36	29.83	39.94	30.48	1.86	24.85	35.04	85.16	N/A	N/A	N/A
Toneva et al. (2018)		Bulgaria	CT	F	70	35.19	2.33	29.83	41.84	29.25	2.11	24.81	33.38	83.27*	5.59	73.40	100.32	
Toneva et al. (2018)		Bulgaria	CT	M	70	36.63	2.93	29.60	43.42	31.47	2.35	26.70	36.35	86.17*	6.23	75.03	104.04	
Macaluso (2011)		France	Dry	F	32	34.90	2.26	30.70	39.40	29.40	2.63	23.70	35.20	84.24	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Macaluso (2011)		France	Dry	M	36	35.38	2.27	31.50	40.50	30.72	2.11	27.30	37.70	86.83	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Chovalopoulou and Bertatos (2017)		Greece	Dry	F	77	34.87	2.41	27.97	40.98	30.62	2.18	24.80	36.52	88.04*	6.76	75.73	108.67	
Chovalopoulou and Bertatos (2017)		Greece	Dry	M	77	36.69	2.47	30.02	42.18	32.48	2.70	26.92	40.01	88.70*	6.87	74.43	104.55	
Kranioti et al. (2008)		Greece	Dry	F	88	34.49	2.31	N/A	N/A	28.85	2.51	N/A	N/A	83.65	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Kranioti et al. (2008)		Greece	Dry	M	90	36.19	2.80	N/A	N/A	31.37	2.80	N/A	N/A	86.68	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Lytzisz et al. (2017)		Greece	Dry	F	68	33.86	2.31	26.70	38.89	28.97	2.32	22.67	34.72	85.56	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Lytzisz et al. (2017)		Greece	Dry	M	73	36.16	2.29	30.74	42.98	31.32	2.51	22.12	36.67	86.62	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Natsis et al. (2013)		Greece	Dry	F	66	34.79	2.39	N/A	N/A	29.61	2.08	N/A	N/A	85.11	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Natsis et al. (2013)		Greece	Dry	M	77	36.20	3.39	N/A	N/A	30.92	3.15	N/A	N/A	85.41	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Luzzi et al. (2019)		Italy	Dry/CT	F/M	75	35.30	N/A	28.20	41.40	30.40	N/A	26.00	36.80	86.12	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Burdan et al. (2012)		Poland	CT	F	171	35.47	2.60	29.00	42.70	30.95	2.71	20.10	37.50	87.55*	8.37	59.47	115.41	
Burdan et al. (2012)		Poland	CT	M	142	37.06	3.07	30.00	48.50	32.98	2.78	24.80	39.70	89.34*	8.35	70.45	128.00	
Guerreiro et al. (2019)		Portugal	Dry	F	101	34.20	2.47	26.51	40.02	29.80	2.38	25.20	36.40	87.31*	6.55	73.93	105.46	
Guerreiro et al. (2019)		Portugal	Dry	M	108	35.35	2.95	22.99	43.45	30.79	2.62	20.09	36.80	87.34*	6.61	70.68	113.05	
Catalina-Herrera (1987)	Spain	Dry	F	26	34.30	N/A	N/A	N/A	29.90	N/A	N/A	N/A	87.17	N/A	N/A	N/A		
Catalina-Herrera (1987)	Spain	Dry	M	74	36.20	N/A	N/A	N/A	31.10	N/A	N/A	N/A	85.91	N/A	N/A	N/A		

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.20

Summarised Summary Statistics from Published Literature

Tab. S3.20: Mean values the summary statistics of FML, FMB and FMI from the published literature and the new Berlin samples. All studies used to calculate the mean values for each population and sex groups are reported in Tab. S3.19. For legend and notes see below.

Continent	Population	NStudies	Sex	n	FML				FMB				FMI			
					Mean	±SD	Min	Max	Mean	±SD	Min	Max	Mean	±SD	Min	Max
Africa	Africa	1	ALL	8	39.27	2.97	33.83	42.66	32.78	4.16	29.69	42.17	83.47	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Egypt	5	F	373	33.21	2.67	26.38	41.75	28.00	2.43	22.13	33.95	84.53	9.38	82.09	86.88
	Egypt	5	M	364	37.02	3.21	20.55	45.28	30.78	2.52	23.50	36.63	83.26	10.35	74.18	88.24
	Egypt	5	ALL	737	35.11	2.94	23.46	43.51	29.39	2.47	22.81	35.29	83.89	9.87	78.14	87.56
	Eritrea	1 (current)	F	7	33.92	2.93	31.00	37.85	27.65	1.09	25.99	28.68	81.85	4.77	75.36	87.30
	Eritrea	1 (current)	M	12	36.27	2.89	30.73	41.87	29.16	2.90	24.50	35.39	80.44	5.61	67.02	86.81
	Eritrea	1 (current)	ALL	21	35.36	2.90	30.73	41.87	28.54	2.36	24.50	35.39	80.88	4.99	67.02	87.30
	Kenya	1	ALL	202	38.50	6.50	N/A	N/A	35.00	7.00	N/A	N/A	90.91	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Nigeria	1	F	10	34.39	3.88	N/A	N/A	28.16	1.99	N/A	N/A	81.88	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Nigeria	1	M	90	36.26	2.39	N/A	N/A	30.09	2.58	N/A	N/A	82.98	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Nigeria	2	ALL	220	35.59	2.96	N/A	N/A	29.27	2.39	N/A	N/A	82.24	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Sudan	1	F	28	36.13	2.72	N/A	N/A	30.29	2.92	N/A	N/A	83.84	N/A	N/A	N/A
Sudan	1	M	72	37.60	3.01	N/A	N/A	30.84	2.67	N/A	N/A	82.02	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Sudan	1	ALL	100	36.87	2.87	N/A	N/A	30.57	2.80	N/A	N/A	82.93	N/A	N/A	N/A	
North America	USA	2	ALL	138	35.27	2.50	29.33	38.33	30.43	2.00	25.67	40.33	86.24	N/A	N/A	N/A
South America	Brazil	3	F	189	33.43	3.00	23.69	40.35	30.17	2.59	22.80	37.16	91.28	8.61	67.92	123.98
	Brazil	3	M	285	34.62	2.96	27.70	42.56	31.47	3.02	23.88	39.80	91.11	10.82	46.00	132.60
	Brazil	5	ALL	591	34.15	2.83	26.35	40.92	30.28	2.80	22.89	37.42	89.16	9.72	56.96	128.29
	Chile	1	F	50	35.60	3.00	N/A	N/A	30.10	2.40	N/A	N/A	84.55	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Chile	1	M	50	37.40	3.30	N/A	N/A	31.90	2.60	N/A	N/A	85.29	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Chile	1	ALL	100	36.50	3.15	N/A	N/A	31.00	2.50	N/A	N/A	84.92	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Peru	1	ALL	59	35.43	3.25	28.80	43.46	32.28	2.80	27.53	39.17	91.11	N/A	N/A	N/A
Asia	Bengal	1	ALL	15	39.09	2.62	35.37	43.63	32.99	2.11	30.52	36.29	84.39	N/A	N/A	N/A
	China	1	F	30	32.10	2.10	N/A	N/A	25.80	1.80	N/A	N/A	80.37	N/A	N/A	N/A
	China	1	M	30	34.10	2.60	N/A	N/A	27.50	2.40	N/A	N/A	80.65	N/A	N/A	N/A
	China	1	ALL	60	33.10	2.35	N/A	N/A	26.65	2.10	N/A	N/A	80.51	N/A	N/A	N/A
	East Asia	1	ALL	7	38.38	2.04	34.60	41.01	33.53	2.72	29.56	36.81	87.36	N/A	N/A	N/A
	India	21	F	1069	32.91	2.57	27.93	39.68	27.79	2.13	23.20	33.88	84.48	N/A	N/A	N/A
	India	21	M	1493	35.38	2.66	29.03	42.92	29.49	2.40	23.77	35.91	83.35	N/A	N/A	N/A

	India	37	ALL	4085	34.30	2.60	28.35	41.19	28.77	2.31	23.02	35.14	83.93	6.60	70.84	95.74
	Iran	1	F	50	34.38	1.47	N/A	N/A	28.34	1.43	N/A	N/A	82.45	7.36	N/A	N/A
	Iran	1	M	50	37.72	1.01	N/A	N/A	31.68	1.30	N/A	N/A	83.97	13.24	N/A	N/A
	Iran	1	ALL	100	36.05	1.24	N/A	N/A	30.01	1.37	N/A	N/A	83.21	10.30	N/A	N/A
	Iraq	1	F	45	32.90	2.00	26.90	38.00	27.30	2.20	22.3	31.80	82.98	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Iraq	1	M	43	34.90	2.00	29.30	40.80	29.50	2.50	24.00	34.80	84.53	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Iraq	1	ALL	88	33.90	2.00	28.10	39.40	28.40	2.35	23.15	33.30	83.75	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Japan	1 (current)	F	4	33.96	2.32	31.52	37.06	29.48	1.89	26.75	30.89	86.91	4.53	82.47	93.04
	Japan	1 (current)	M	4	36.55	1.06	35.02	37.46	31.88	0.83	30.78	32.54	87.30	4.52	82.15	92.90
	Japan	1 (current)	ALL	11	35.07	1.94	31.52	37.46	30.18	1.92	26.75	32.54	86.08	3.98	81.71	93.04
	Malaysia	1	ALL	15	38.59	2.80	33.60	41.75	33.31	2.37	29.59	36.81	86.32	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Nepal	1	F	43	30.70	2.28	N/A	N/A	25.19	2.03	N/A	N/A	82.05	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Nepal	1	M	53	33.45	2.25	N/A	N/A	27.64	2.02	N/A	N/A	82.63	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Nepal	1	ALL	96	32.08	2.27	N/A	N/A	26.42	2.03	N/A	N/A	82.34	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Oman	1	F	17	33.22	2.00	29.50	34.75	29.49	1.66	26	31.75	88.77	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Oman	1	M	19	36.78	1.52	35.00	39.75	30.05	2.36	25.75	34.25	81.70	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Oman	1	ALL	36	35.00	1.76	32.25	37.25	29.77	2.01	25.88	33.00	85.24	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Saudi Arabia	1	F	100	36.10	2.65	31.00	47.00	30.6	2.47	26.00	43.00	84.96	6.39	71.79	107.89
	Saudi Arabia	1	M	100	37.21	2.15	31.00	41.00	31.56	2.25	25.00	36.00	85.22	6.35	68.29	100
	Saudi Arabia	1	ALL	200	36.66	2.40	31.00	44.00	31.08	2.36	25.50	39.50	85.09	6.37	70.04	103.95
	Turkey	6	F	385	34.42	3.07	27.60	41.80	29.54	2.41	24.80	34.30	85.45	7.67	N/A	N/A
	Turkey	6	M	330	36.41	2.89	31.10	42.70	31.22	2.51	26.70	39.40	85.85	9.27	N/A	N/A
	Turkey	14	ALL	1286	35.41	2.88	28.89	42.59	30.06	3.54	25.56	32.59	84.83	8.47	N/A	N/A
Europe	Europe	1	ALL	17	38.55	3.91	31.35	45.42	33.27	3.70	26.56	40.54	86.30	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Britain	2	F	148	34.75	1.94	30.32	40.74	29.36	2.01	25.27	36.25	84.49	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Britain	2	M	145	35.85	2.39	30.32	41.31	30.50	1.82	24.85	35.04	85.06	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Britain	2	ALL	293	35.30	2.16	30.32	41.02	29.93	1.91	25.06	35.65	84.78	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Bulgaria	1	F	70	35.19	2.33	29.83	41.84	29.25	2.11	24.81	33.38	83.27	5.59	73.4	100.32
	Bulgaria	1	M	70	36.63	2.93	29.60	43.42	31.47	2.35	26.70	36.35	86.17	6.23	75.03	104.04
	Bulgaria	1	ALL	140	35.91	2.63	29.72	42.63	30.36	2.23	25.76	34.87	84.72	5.91	74.22	102.18
	France	1	F	32	34.90	2.26	30.70	39.40	29.40	2.63	23.70	35.20	84.24	N/A	N/A	N/A
	France	1	M	36	35.38	2.27	31.50	40.50	30.72	2.11	27.30	37.70	86.83	N/A	N/A	N/A
	France	1	ALL	68	35.14	2.27	31.10	39.95	30.06	2.37	25.50	36.45	85.53	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Germany	1 (current)	F	19	35.69	2.44	32.38	39.65	30.25	1.98	25.68	32.97	84.94	5.86	74.06	98.15
	Germany	1 (current)	M	23	36.52	2.60	30.94	40.17	30.39	2.12	26.42	34.79	83.40	5.40	72.69	94.53
	Germany	1 (current)	ALL	49	36.11	2.46	30.94	40.17	30.55	2.17	25.68	34.79	84.79	5.71	72.69	98.15
	Greece	4	F	299	34.50	2.36	27.34	39.94	29.51	2.27	23.74	35.62	85.59	6.76	75.73	108.67
Greece	4	M	317	36.31	2.74	30.38	42.58	31.52	2.79	24.52	38.34	86.85	6.87	74.43	104.55	

Greece	4	ALL	616	35.41	2.55	28.86	41.26	30.52	2.53	24.13	36.98	86.22	6.82	75.08	106.61
Greece	1 (current)	F	7	35.04	2.70	30.26	38.11	29.46	2.21	26.04	33.58	84.20	4.73	76.89	90.66
Greece	1 (current)	M	7	34.76	3.06	30.61	39.76	29.82	2.53	26.89	34.49	85.90	3.75	80.00	92.24
Greece	1 (current)	ALL	17	35.40	3.04	30.26	42.03	29.96	2.38	26.04	34.49	16.98	4.91	84.83	76.89
Italy	1	ALL	75	35.30	N/A	28.20	41.40	30.40	N/A	26.00	36.80	86.12	N/A	N/A	N/A
Poland	1	F	171	35.47	2.60	29.00	42.70	30.95	2.71	20.10	37.50	87.55	8.37	59.47	115.41
Poland	1	M	142	37.06	3.07	30.00	48.50	32.98	2.78	24.80	39.70	89.34	8.35	70.45	128
Poland	1	ALL	313	36.27	2.84	29.50	45.60	31.97	2.75	22.45	38.60	88.45	8.36	64.96	121.71
Portugal	1	F	101	34.20	2.47	26.51	40.02	29.80	2.38	25.20	36.40	87.31	6.55	73.93	105.46
Portugal	1	M	108	35.35	2.95	22.99	43.45	30.79	2.62	20.09	36.80	87.34	6.61	70.68	113.05
Portugal	1	ALL	209	34.78	2.71	24.75	41.74	30.30	2.50	22.65	36.60	87.33	6.58	72.31	109.26
Spain	1	F	26	34.3	N/A	N/A	N/A	29.9	N/A	N/A	N/A	87.17	N/A	N/A	N/A
Spain	1	M	74	36.2	N/A	N/A	N/A	31.10	N/A	N/A	N/A	85.91	N/A	N/A	N/A
Spain	1	ALL	100	35.25	N/A	N/A	N/A	30.50	N/A	N/A	N/A	86.54	N/A	N/A	N/A

FML = foramen magnum length, FMB = foramen magnum breadth, FMI = foramen magnum index, F = female, M = male, ALL = sum of sex known (F and M) and sex unknown individuals (ind), n = number of individuals, $\pm$ SD = standard deviation, Min = minimum value, Max = maximum value, N/A = data not available, current = data collected for this study. Note that no mean summary data for sex-unidentified (ind) subsamples were calculated, as only the data for sex-known/separated datasets and sex-unknown/pooled datasets are needed for the current intra- and interpopulation analyses respectively. For the sex-pooled interpopulation analyses, sex-unknown individuals were added to the sex-known ones. This also explains any present offset between the counts of ALL of each population and F or M subgroups of the same population.

Supplementary Material, Results/Dicussion – S3.21

Foramen Magnum Shape Categories across the Published Literature

Tab. S3.21: Summary of FM shape categories used among different FM studies. For notes see below. n = number of shape categories used in the respective study. X = shape category was used, - = shape category was not used.

Study	n	Egg	Round/ Circle	Oval	Pear	Rhomboid	Diamond	Tetra- gonal	Penta- gonal	Hexagonal	Irregular (A)	Irregular (B)	Other/ Additional
Aghakhani et al. (2016)	6	-	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	-
Akay et al. (2017)	8	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	-
Burdan et al. (2012)*	8	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X
Chethan et al. (2012)	7	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	X
Crider (2010)*	5	X	X	X	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
Devadas et al. 2017	6	-	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	-	X	X	-
Fathima and Babu (2016)	5	X	X	X	-	-	-	-	X	X	-	-	-
Govsa et al. (2011)*	8	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	X
Ilhan et al. (2017)	7	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	-
Khudaverdyan (2011)	4	X	X	X	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
Kumar et al. (2015)	5	-	X	X	-	-	-	X	-	X	X	-	-
Kumar et al. (2019)	4	-	-	X	-	-	X	-	X	X	-	-	-
Loyal et al. (2013)*	3	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X
Mittal et al. (2018)	6	-	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	-
Mishra et al. (2018)	6	-	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	-
Murshed et al. (2003)	8	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	-
Natsis et al. (2013)*	8	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	-	-	X	-	X
Pires et al. (2016)	5	-	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	-	-	-
Radhakrishnan et al. (2012)*	9	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	X
Raikar et al. (2016)	7	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	-
Rajkumar et al. (2017)	5	-	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	-	-	-
Remya et al. (2017)	6	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	-	X	X	-	-
Revankar et al. (2020)	7	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	-
Sampada et al. (2017)	7	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	-
Sharma and Mehra (2018)	7	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	-
Sharma et al. (2015)	7	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	-
Sharma et al. (2020)	7	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	-
Singh et al. (2019)	7	-	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	-
Singh et al. (2020)	7	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	-
Tubbs et al. (2010a)*	5	X	X	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	X
Veeramani et al. (2018)	7	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	-
Vinutha et al. (2018)	8	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	-
Total	-	21	31	30	2	2	3	24	24	25	23	4	7

Notes:

n = total number of shape categories

*In Burdan et al. (2012) a completely different set of FM shapes, which could not be found in any other study, was used: circular, two semicircles, heart-like, wide oval, bi-rounded oval, ventrally wide oval, bi-pointed oval, and dorsally convergent oval.

*Crider (2010) used an "arrowhead" shape category in addition.

*Govsa et al. (2011) also used a shape category "that is formed by the combination of two different semi-circles" (p. 1074).

*Loyal et al. (2013) used a "polygonal" shape category.

*Natsis et al. (2013) also used 'two semicircles' as additional shape category.

*Radhakrishnan et al. (2012) also used a 'trigonal' shape category and a total of three different irregular shapes that are not described in further detail.

*Tubbs et al. (2010a) additionally used two-semicircle- and elongated circle shape categories.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.22.1 and S3.22.2

PC Selection (Scree-plot) and Shape-PCA Summary Report – Entire Sample

Fig. S3.22.1: Shape-PCA scree-plot of the entire dataset ($n = 98$) showing the explained percentage variance of each PC (grey bars) plotted against a generated broken stick model distribution (red bars) in descending order beginning with PC1 on the left. PCs that explain more variance than estimated by the broken stick model, i.e., when PCs bars exceed the red BSM bars, are considered meaningful enough to be retained for further analysis. Here, the first eleven PCs explain more variance (80.66%) than predicted by the BSM and are therefore selected.

Tab. S3.22.2: Summary report of the most meaningful shape-PCs (PC1 to PC11) that explain 80.66% of variance derived from the shape PCA performed on the entire dataset ($n = 98$).

Value	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8	PC9	PC10	PC11
Eigenvalues	0.0009256868	0.0005234748	0.0003923027	0.0003335319	0.0002917775	0.0001846437	0.0001508275	0.0001384953	0.0001222043	0.0001067276	9.211543e-05
Explained variance	0.2289	0.1294	0.0970	0.08247	0.07214	0.04566	0.0373	0.0343	0.0302	0.0264	0.0228
Cumulative proportion	0.2289	0.3584	0.4553	0.5378	0.6100	0.6556	0.6929	0.7272	0.7574	0.7838	0.8066

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.23.1 and S3.23.2

PC Selection (Scree-plot) and Shape-PCA Summary Report – Sex-known Sample

Fig. S3.23.1: Shape-PCA scree-plot of the sex-known dataset (n = 83) showing the explained percentage variance of each PC (grey bars) plotted against a generated broken stick model distribution (red bars) in descending order beginning with PC1 on the left. PCs that explain more variance than estimated by the broken stick model, i.e., when PCs bars exceed the red BSM bars, are considered meaningful enough to be retained for further analysis. Here, the first nine PCs explain more variance (75.58%) than predicted by the BSM and are therefore selected.

Tab. S3.23.2: Summary report of the most meaningful shape-PCs (PC1 to PC9) that explain 75.58% of variance derived from the shape PCA performed on the entire dataset (n = 83).

Value	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8	PC9
Eigenvalues	0.0007930752	0.0005457242	0.0004151841	0.0003470644	0.000256526	0.000192501	0.0001511052	0.0001459537	0.0001216846
Explained variance	0.2019177487	0.1389419226	0.1057062855	0.0883629475	0.065311788	0.049010960	0.0384715353	0.0371599702	0.0309810226
Cumulative proportion	0.2019177487	0.3408596713	0.4465659568	0.5349289043	0.600240693	0.649251653	0.6877231882	0.7248831583	0.7558641810

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.24.1 and S3.24.2
PC Selection (Scree-plot) and From-PCA Summary Report – Entire Sample

Fig. 3.24.1: From-PCA scree-plot of the entire dataset (n = 98) showing the explained percentage variance of each PC (grey bars) plotted against a generated broken stick model distribution (red bars) in descending order beginning with PC1 on the left. PCs that explain more variance than estimated by the broken stick model, i.e., when PCs bars exceed the red BSM bars, are considered meaningful enough to be retained for further analysis. Here, the first ten PCs explain more variance (80.19%) than predicted by the BSM and are therefore selected.

Tab. 3.24.2: Summary report of the most meaningful form-PCs (PC1 to PC10) that explain 80.19% of variance derived from the shape PCA performed on the entire dataset (n = 98).

Value	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8	PC9	PC10
Eigenvalues	0.03077	0.02952	0.02283	0.01980	0.01824	0.01662	0.01359	0.01220	0.01177	0.01105
Explained variance	0.19299	0.17760	0.10625	0.07995	0.06778	0.05630	0.03762	0.03034	0.02822	0.02487
Cumulative proportion	0.19299	0.37059	0.47685	0.55680	0.62458	0.68088	0.71850	0.74884	0.77706	0.80193

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.25.1 and S3.25.2

PC Selection (Scree-plot) and From-PCA Summary Report – Sex-known Sample

Fig. S3.25.1: From-PCA scree-plot of the sex-known dataset ($n = 83$) showing the explained percentage variance of each PC (grey bars) plotted against a generated broken stick model distribution (red bars) in descending order beginning with PC1 on the left. PCs that explain more variance than estimated by the broken stick model, i.e., when PCs bars exceed the red BSM bars, are considered meaningful enough to be retained for further analysis. Here, the first nine PCs explain more variance (77.70%) than predicted by the BSM and are therefore selected.

Tab. S3.25.2: Summary report of the most meaningful form-PCs (PC1 to PC9) that explain 77.70% of variance derived from the shape PCA performed on the entire dataset ($n = 83$).

Value	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8	PC9
Eigenvalues	0.03116	0.02674	0.02336	0.02036	0.01835	0.01594	0.01387	0.01225	0.01203
Explained variance	0.20257	0.14920	0.11387	0.08646	0.07027	0.05302	0.04017	0.03129	0.03020
Cumulative proportion	0.20257	0.35176	0.46563	0.55209	0.62236	0.67538	0.71555	0.74684	0.77704

RV 1616	Germany	0.00377579	-0.04261505	-0.02970046	-0.03798157	-0.02355536	0.00082127	0.00034944	-0.00753642	0.00875245
RV 1618	Germany	0.01624947	-0.01277342	1.87E-05	0.01138189	0.01756727	-0.02499741	-0.00111448	0.0190755	-0.00707568
RV 1625	Germany	0.04979866	-0.01436931	0.00912207	0.01769977	-0.00864687	0.00390136	-0.01872281	-0.0223427	0.00873578
RV 1630	Germany	0.01064829	0.03096865	-0.00179862	-0.02188257	0.01205991	0.01184574	-0.01246486	0.00409709	0.01312351
RV 1633	Germany	0.04029895	-0.03138278	-0.01507528	-0.0129479	0.00621041	-0.01488944	0.01352582	-0.01023849	-0.00465514
RV 1636	Germany	0.00397456	-0.00125879	0.00043849	0.01464586	-0.00478879	0.01067968	0.01541092	0.00252252	0.01534957
RV 1638	Germany	0.0110293	0.00489604	-0.00767715	-0.00143061	0.03132333	0.00040042	0.01440084	-0.01341906	-0.01910592
RV 1640	Germany	0.02760272	-0.02435355	-0.01248404	0.02031722	0.02977717	-0.02107102	-0.00386736	-0.00453679	0.00472884
RV 1656	Germany	-0.01815814	-0.00156082	0.01966193	0.02536714	0.00731585	-0.00649156	-0.01589255	0.00801691	-0.00101028
RV 1657	Germany	-0.0341475	0.02698311	-0.02060432	-0.02899859	0.00080239	-0.01328811	0.01661911	0.01245159	-0.01106235
S 158	Germany	0.02436896	-0.00782961	-0.00605829	-0.00430352	-0.00260952	0.00863016	0.01156701	-0.0032936	-0.00446731
S 159	Germany	-0.02473825	0.02027735	0.03028404	-0.00258517	0.02636168	-0.00175155	-0.01781098	0.01830858	-0.00455302
S 162	Germany	0.02669454	-0.00822681	-0.01817224	-0.00306464	0.00711945	-0.00939086	0.01219999	0.01155266	0.01192075
S 4541	Germany	0.01098065	0.04134846	-0.02982713	0.02965854	-0.00335326	0.03387496	-0.01136536	-0.00378802	-0.01059163
S 4585	Germany	-0.02410363	0.02371628	-0.04190863	-0.0045719	0.01507897	0.02876402	-0.02532632	0.01475407	-0.00478327
S 4631	Germany	-0.01321964	-0.01873928	-0.04686884	-0.00876193	0.01184549	0.01191329	0.00401575	0.01984506	0.00616233
S 5164	Germany	-0.01559658	-0.00058862	0.01432196	-0.01534876	-0.01372729	-0.00954855	0.00393906	0.01133022	-0.00421482
S 5165	Germany	0.01601711	0.01581292	-0.00088352	-0.01230716	0.00039824	1.35E-05	-0.00154764	0.00671352	0.00227576
RSK 501	Greece	0.03097752	0.00828385	0.00886567	-0.03384401	0.00816736	0.02865557	0.00672947	-0.00374671	0.01327383
RSK 502	Greece	0.01486567	0.05267119	-0.00348534	-0.01563033	-0.00908832	-0.00057431	-0.00745661	-0.01146534	0.01984668
RSK 503	Greece	-0.01228521	-0.01970489	0.01756372	-0.00350348	-0.00961551	-0.00549243	-0.00188852	-0.00642562	-0.01975579
RSK 504	Greece	0.02963291	0.032842	-0.01593858	-0.01915653	-0.01101393	-0.02435092	0.00727994	-0.01535173	-0.00711658
RSK 505	Greece	-0.0410999	-0.00649768	0.01803609	-0.02970585	-0.00877103	0.01483103	0.00185659	0.00381491	0.00273976
RSK 506	Greece	-0.01794994	-0.03852617	-0.00161124	-0.00994834	0.00348001	-0.00737462	-0.00131914	0.00600673	-0.00634141
RV 1119	Greece	-0.03723912	-0.02527579	-0.01175012	0.01254991	0.01721017	-0.009941	-0.00236854	-0.02392359	0.01961389
RV 1120	Greece	-0.04146011	0.01965743	-0.02560269	0.00587277	-0.0334	-0.01681542	-0.01580896	-0.00285206	-0.01050304
RV 1122	Greece	0.02572323	0.03206197	0.00954497	-0.0308599	-0.00577331	0.01433888	0.00850834	0.01321721	-0.01186164
RV 1123	Greece	0.01213031	0.04618137	0.01344367	0.01649509	0.00289353	-0.01843327	0.0028664	0.00385496	-0.00167854
RV 1842	Greece	0.00471752	-0.01696446	-0.00705535	0.01229492	0.02991269	-0.01325783	-0.00072366	0.02025822	-0.00873601
RV 1845	Greece	0.04325239	-0.02712507	0.02579973	0.00433819	0.00318454	0.02673076	-0.0005381	0.00331082	0.00356451
RV 1846	Greece	0.01614235	0.00017612	-0.0289185	-0.03117127	-0.00394425	0.01330674	-0.01099163	-0.01123137	-0.01448643
RV 1847	Greece	0.00744433	0.00587736	-0.01662575	0.01431631	-0.00148096	-0.00196359	0.00279467	0.01988876	0.00989349

RV 1616	Germany	-0.00873863	0.00298156	-0.04280637	0.02799393	0.03927112	0.02166087	-0.00081765	0.00117134	0.00771788
RV 1618	Germany	-0.0422984	0.00797906	-0.01309077	-0.0010928	-0.017234	-0.01460819	0.02504113	-0.00162707	-0.02095151
RV 1625	Germany	-0.02967951	-0.04137088	-0.01407243	-0.00779895	-0.0159462	0.00901161	-0.00389819	0.02302995	0.01798041
RV 1630	Germany	0.00799197	-0.01689457	0.03114129	0.00180092	0.02468099	-0.01518436	-0.01194328	0.00943064	-0.00438178
RV 1633	Germany	-0.00305382	-0.04500524	-0.03101423	0.01578396	0.01711877	-0.00861498	0.0148516	-0.01184258	0.01418602
RV 1636	Germany	0.02823734	-0.02418499	-0.00080737	0.00172476	-0.00905479	0.00308568	-0.01072263	-0.01729855	0.00339119
RV 1638	Germany	-0.04788599	0.01936507	0.00437136	0.00539557	-0.00721829	-0.02766771	-0.00031606	-0.0092252	0.01382984
RV 1640	Germany	-0.0158936	-0.02299456	-0.02420512	0.01336687	-0.02058492	-0.02910145	0.02104534	0.00436604	0.00412901
RV 1656	Germany	0.02671887	0.00258738	-0.00134795	-0.01807581	-0.02418164	-0.00699274	0.00646106	0.01356861	-0.01125493
RV 1657	Germany	-0.00109198	0.04338177	0.02645577	0.01808519	0.0253536	-0.00063644	0.01331367	-0.01842072	-0.0092123
S 158	Germany	-0.01733849	-0.01751511	-0.00777321	0.00600756	0.00484463	0.00236774	-0.00862102	-0.01067915	0.00598544
S 159	Germany	0.03076843	0.00909599	0.02039567	-0.02989768	0.00256578	-0.02784242	0.00165976	0.01226793	-0.02064448
S 162	Germany	-0.03284338	-0.00972996	-0.00836	0.01742239	0.0012349	-0.00633871	0.00940998	-0.01419645	-0.00881414
S 4541	Germany	-0.00732037	-0.00883217	0.04142757	0.03110569	-0.02811057	0.00478889	-0.03385138	0.01273062	-3.20E-06
S 4585	Germany	-0.02081947	0.04353584	0.0231007	0.03977447	-0.00045822	-0.01329472	-0.02875759	0.02255128	-0.02166842
S 4631	Germany	-0.00347273	0.0193694	-0.01903384	0.04570726	-0.0183544	-0.01192434	-0.00818516	-0.01868873	
S 5164	Germany	0.03638062	-0.00509311	-0.00032729	-0.01365602	0.01972121	0.0108604	0.00949398	-0.00747189	-0.00877071
S 5165	Germany	-0.00785222	-0.01354859	0.01588276	0.00074413	0.01353636	-0.00180975	-5.09E-05	-0.00071333	-0.00593817
RSK 501	Greece	-0.02266799	-0.02045679	0.00828011	-0.01015063	0.03311609	-0.009929	-0.0286859	-0.00659909	0.00638573
RSK 502	Greece	0.0032529	-0.0190192	0.05285483	0.00376917	0.0190546	0.00679725	0.00053139	0.00860559	0.01125184
RSK 503	Greece	-0.00453319	0.01737201	-0.01989456	-0.01839402	0.00069981	0.01090068	0.00554208	0.00449489	0.00412893
RSK 504	Greece	-0.07229487	0.01353699	0.03221344	0.01288593	0.01184923	0.01412267	0.02447178	-0.00136831	0.01360924
RSK 505	Greece	0.01168096	0.04263527	-0.00690726	-0.02029108	0.02566427	0.0090626	-0.01479631	-0.0017659	-0.00449323
RSK 506	Greece	0.02748342	0.00381517	-0.0384325	0.00173001	0.01181677	-0.00506187	0.0073353	-0.00050253	-0.00566632
RV 1119	Greece	0.01616887	0.03361249	-0.02551354	0.01139942	-0.01520245	-0.01563639	0.00995951	0.00738636	0.02336117
RV 1120	Greece	0.03086777	0.02916049	0.01955335	0.02592	-0.00319168	0.03345107	0.01684556	0.01704153	-0.00215701
RV 1122	Greece	-0.0431687	-0.00103525	0.03176201	-0.01174413	0.02704027	0.00595455	-0.01431003	-0.0104116	-0.01216294
RV 1123	Greece	0.00971895	-0.02136483	0.04650074	-0.01185384	-0.01417127	-0.00312041	0.01841944	-0.00383546	-0.00292224
RV 1842	Greece	0.0344997	-0.02848899	-0.01646877	0.00918672	-0.00718759	-0.03246346	0.01314584	-0.00545515	-0.01793614
RV 1845	Greece	-0.07424791	-0.00368737	-0.02749784	-0.02755548	-0.01247443	0.00075689	-0.02663908	0.00171965	-0.00582361
RV 1846	Greece	-0.03807219	0.00782585	-0.00023641	0.02643184	0.0279961	0.0041689	-0.0132735	0.01446285	0.00672164
RV 1847	Greece	-0.02435943	0.00667368	0.00568265	0.01634909	-0.01645475	0.00344322	0.00199946	-0.00634364	-0.01977156

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.30

Allometric regression and 2B-PLS – Entire Dataset

Tab. S3.30: Allometric data of the Procrustes-aligned entire dataset (n = 98).

ID	Population	Log(Centroid Size)	Two-block Partial Least Squares Analysis	
			Block 1 (X Scores)	Block 2 (Y Scores)
RV 1065	Eritrea	4.581563273	0.033719596	-0.007790824
RV 1283	Eritrea	4.520826426	0.094456443	0.026138725
RV 1284	Eritrea	4.615801406	-0.000518536	0.005410068
RV 1285	Eritrea	4.613519728	0.001763141	0.006271393
RV 1288	Eritrea	4.635050486	-0.019767617	-0.009914778
RV 1289	Eritrea	4.453781531	0.161501338	-0.013013156
RV 1290	Eritrea	4.515575661	0.099707208	0.002085539
RV 1291	Eritrea	4.673168810	-0.057885941	-0.009675223
RV 1293	Eritrea	4.648190250	-0.032907381	0.009555627
RV 1294	Eritrea	4.474718220	0.140564649	0.010667363
RV 1296	Eritrea	4.593142156	0.022140713	-0.005293066
RV 1298	Eritrea	4.611364756	0.003918113	-0.007296428
RV 1300	Eritrea	4.789054138	-0.173771269	-0.018754297
RV 1301	Eritrea	4.551578209	0.063704661	0.020913928
RV 1302	Eritrea	4.637992460	-0.022709591	-0.014661069
RV 1303	Eritrea	4.637156286	-0.021873417	-0.043600518
RV 1304	Eritrea	4.598046731	0.017236138	0.030915886
RV 1305	Eritrea	4.585001477	0.030281392	0.020063668
RV 1306	Eritrea	4.612802175	0.002480695	0.007984701
RV 1307	Eritrea	4.491415046	0.123867823	-0.017727302
RV 1309	Eritrea	4.643111696	-0.027828827	-0.010868322
RV 37	Japan	4.636227089	0.01272761	0.01074705
RV 1067	Japan	4.618203368	0.02571594	-0.02604232
RV 2148	Japan	4.535517328	-0.00681009	-0.00321564
S 4033	Japan	4.594923058	0.020359811	-0.005334359
S 4034	Japan	4.610205661	0.005077208	-0.013575614
S 4035	Japan	4.637317580	-0.022034710	-0.003390872
S 4036	Japan	4.491121543	0.124161326	0.013888867
S 4037	Japan	4.573370589	0.041912280	0.011565972
S 4038	Japan	4.608551572	0.006731297	-0.007575027
S 4039	Japan	4.661626961	-0.046344092	-0.003726138
S 4632	Japan	4.656875730	-0.041592861	0.000682351
RV 376	Germany	4.709089389	-0.093806520	-0.013544846
RV 389	Germany	4.562391008	0.052891861	0.001119951
RV 613	Germany	4.656869380	-0.041586511	-0.023053657
RV 614	Germany	4.689440844	-0.074157974	0.013806559
RV 615	Germany	4.565165889	0.050116980	0.020149983
RV 721	Germany	4.686576421	-0.071293551	-0.022153162
RV 724	Germany	4.716282528	-0.10099659	-0.003242885
RV 725	Germany	4.703306892	-0.088024022	-0.011250937
RV 726	Germany	4.516061299	0.099221571	-0.013263665
RV 778	Germany	4.648186001	-0.032903132	-0.001251242
RV 782	Germany	4.642121447	-0.026838578	-0.017447438
RV 783	Germany	4.602628701	0.012654169	-0.018859162
RV 786	Germany	4.732595737	-0.117312868	0.019685397
RV 834	Germany	4.586667738	0.028615131	0.030078860
RV 870	Germany	4.700861918	-0.085579049	-0.006394087
RV 872	Germany	4.623664288	-0.008381419	0.010945208
RV 879	Germany	4.567172113	0.048110756	0.000264457
RV 884	Germany	4.631212853	-0.015929983	0.020661834
RV 886	Germany	4.581548416	0.033734453	-0.011635477
RV 890	Germany	4.726293409	-0.11010539	-0.017454277
RV 899	Germany	4.656004402	-0.040721532	-0.014741568
RV 901	Germany	4.633528308	-0.018245439	-0.012906502
RV 903	Germany	4.674673635	-0.059390766	0.023377287
RV 905	Germany	4.583032267	0.032250602	0.002933854
RV 923	Germany	4.576782400	0.038500470	0.002979363
RV 959	Germany	4.603400163	0.011882706	0.008250625
RV 1007	Germany	4.668027942	-0.052745073	0.016753485
RV 1124	Germany	4.624091902	-0.008809033	0.017753779
RV 1613	Germany	4.726715427	-0.111432558	-0.027274734
RV 1615	Germany	4.694641079	-0.079358210	-0.020626765
RV 1616	Germany	4.605554654	0.009728215	0.007501520
RV 1618	Germany	4.517680402	0.097602468	0.012452149
RV 1625	Germany	4.598477780	0.016805089	-0.002951223
RV 1630	Germany	4.656930488	-0.041647619	0.008025268
RV 1633	Germany	4.676236913	-0.060954043	0.032792463
RV 1636	Germany	4.691904889	-0.076622020	-0.009412143
RV 1638	Germany	4.504251438	0.111031431	0.029085631
RV 1639	Germany	4.694663844	-0.079380975	-0.024366847
RV 1640	Germany	4.609257254	0.006025615	0.022267252
RV 1656	Germany	4.649846278	-0.034563408	-0.015022591
RV 1657	Germany	4.566960036	0.048322833	-0.003728958
S 158	Germany	4.603326296	0.011956573	0.004791510
S 159	Germany	4.658376034	-0.043093164	-0.004066674
S 162	Germany	4.566419855	0.048863015	0.019448730
S 4541	Germany	4.605137854	0.010145016	-0.004115526
S 4585	Germany	4.521721284	0.093561585	0.002521552
S 4631	Germany	4.590328493	0.024954376	0.016403272
S 5164	Germany	4.691360621	-0.076077751	-0.013725175
S 5165	Germany	4.617126433	-0.001843564	0.001445483
RSK 501	Greece	4.608638724	0.006644145	0.023668825
RSK 502	Greece	4.648937044	-0.033654174	-0.007574338
RSK 503	Greece	4.580248474	0.035034396	-0.007061848

RSK 504	Greece	4.465144281	0.150138588	0.004840397
RSK 505	Greece	4.590828539	0.024454331	0.000343124
RSK 506	Greece	4.665986307	-0.050703438	0.004008346
RV 1119	Greece	4.599017695	0.016265174	-0.002210553
RV 1120	Greece	4.632978485	-0.017695616	-0.032930755
RV 1121	Greece	4.775406976	-0.160124107	-0.014253018
RV 1122	Greece	4.539637706	0.075645163	0.008466971
RV 1123	Greece	4.656127278	-0.040844409	-0.003487671
RV 1842	Greece	4.716277228	-0.100994359	0.018309282
RV 1844	Greece	4.590833374	0.024449496	-0.012962743
RV 1845	Greece	4.468478562	0.146804308	0.017042198
RV 1846	Greece	4.544775434	0.070507435	0.020865687
RV 1847	Greece	4.552820239	0.062462631	0.001475444
RV 1848	Greece	4.640188803	-0.024905933	-0.006981461

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.31

Allometric regression and 2B-PLS – Sex-known Dataset

Tab. S3.31: Allometric data of the Procrustes-aligned sex-known dataset (n = 83).

ID	Population	Log(Centroid Size)	Two-block Partial Least Squares Analysis	
			Block 1 (X Scores)	Block 2 (Y Scores)
RV 1065	Eritrea	4.58156327	0.031266517	-0.030569677
RV 1283	Eritrea	4.52082643	0.092003364	0.018608608
RV 1284	Eritrea	4.61580141	-0.002971615	-0.001597564
RV 1285	Eritrea	4.61351973	-0.000689937	-0.003770809
RV 1288	Eritrea	4.63505049	-0.022220696	-0.006526467
RV 1289	Eritrea	4.45378153	0.159048259	-0.019163808
RV 1290	Eritrea	4.51557566	0.097254129	-0.006353811
RV 1291	Eritrea	4.67316881	-0.060339020	-0.015157529
RV 1293	Eritrea	4.64819025	-0.035360460	0.002678436
RV 1294	Eritrea	4.47471822	0.138111570	0.019693250
RV 1296	Eritrea	4.59314216	0.019687634	0.008840069
RV 1298	Eritrea	4.61136476	0.001465034	-0.017501859
RV 1300	Eritrea	4.78905414	-0.176224348	-0.001068037
RV 1301	Eritrea	4.55157821	0.061251582	0.033405007
RV 1302	Eritrea	4.63799246	-0.025162670	0.009258663
RV 1303	Eritrea	4.63715629	-0.024326496	-0.036359744
RV 1306	Eritrea	4.61280218	0.000027600	0.017857232
RV 1307	Eritrea	4.49141505	0.121414744	-0.015501902
RV 1309	Eritrea	4.64311117	-0.030281905	-0.024505625
RV 37	Japan	4.63622709	-0.023397299	-0.021713360
RV 1067	Japan	4.61820337	-0.005373578	-0.028737986
S 4033	Japan	4.59492306	0.017906733	-0.012566459
S 4035	Japan	4.63731758	-0.024487789	0.009079231
S 4036	Japan	4.49112154	0.121708247	0.026781403
S 4037	Japan	4.57337059	0.039459201	0.011147501
S 4039	Japan	4.66162696	-0.048797171	0.004788636
S 4632	Japan	4.65687573	-0.044045940	-0.007773321
RV 376	Germany	4.70908939	-0.096259599	-0.004276055
RV 389	Germany	4.56239101	0.050438782	0.013211105
RV 613	Germany	4.65686938	-0.044039589	-0.036846277
RV 614	Germany	4.68944084	-0.076611053	-0.001147753
RV 721	Germany	4.68657642	-0.073746630	-0.022455597
RV 724	Germany	4.71628253	-0.103452737	-0.015578892
RV 726	Germany	4.5160613	0.096768492	-0.006060528
RV 778	Germany	4.648186	-0.035356211	0.018104212
RV 782	Germany	4.64212145	-0.029291656	-0.033546285
RV 783	Germany	4.6026287	0.010201090	-0.025263984
RV 870	Germany	4.70086192	-0.088032127	0.005610843
RV 879	Germany	4.56717211	0.045657678	0.000905900
RV 884	Germany	4.63121285	-0.018383062	0.039974380
RV 886	Germany	4.58154842	0.031281375	-0.019117532
RV 890	Germany	4.72629341	-0.113463618	-0.035032831
RV 899	Germany	4.6560044	-0.043174611	-0.000417308
RV 901	Germany	4.63352831	-0.020698517	-0.062405759
RV 903	Germany	4.67467364	-0.061843845	0.003005727
RV 923	Germany	4.5767824	0.036047391	0.016390418
RV 959	Germany	4.60340016	0.009429628	0.002323106
RV 1007	Germany	4.66802794	-0.055198152	0.023540320
RV 1124	Germany	4.6240919	-0.011262112	0.036928697
RV 1613	Germany	4.72671543	-0.113885637	-0.025572881
RV 1615	Germany	4.69464108	-0.081811289	-0.002703504
RV 1616	Germany	4.60555465	0.007275136	0.020100834
RV 1618	Germany	4.5176804	0.095149389	0.009127535
RV 1625	Germany	4.59847778	0.014352010	0.019119741
RV 1630	Germany	4.65693049	-0.044100698	0.012690627
RV 1633	Germany	4.67623691	-0.063407122	0.042389486
RV 1636	Germany	4.69190489	-0.079075098	-0.008760653
RV 1638	Germany	4.50425144	0.108578352	0.023378233
RV 1640	Germany	4.60925725	0.003572536	0.015777012
RV 1656	Germany	4.64984628	-0.037016487	-0.026965042
RV 1657	Germany	4.56696004	0.045869754	-0.007362942
S 158	Germany	4.6033263	0.009503495	0.017428516
S 159	Germany	4.65837603	-0.045546243	-0.021037934
S 162	Germany	4.56641986	0.046409936	0.024830152

S 4541	Germany	4.60513785	0.007691937	0.000782364
S 4585	Germany	4.52172128	0.091108506	-0.009184959
S 4631	Germany	4.59032849	0.022501297	0.003204569
S 5164	Germany	4.69136062	-0.078530830	-0.010098078
S 5165	Germany	4.61712643	-0.004296643	0.010996662
RSK 501	Greece	4.60863872	0.004191066	0.038333552
RSK 502	Greece	4.64893704	-0.036107253	0.014182704
RSK 503	Greece	4.58024847	0.032581317	-0.008041522
RSK 504	Greece	4.46514428	0.147685510	0.034878607
RSK 505	Greece	4.59082854	0.022001252	-0.010444639
RSK 506	Greece	4.66598631	-0.053156516	-0.004850736
RV 1119	Greece	4.5990177	0.013812095	-0.025976383
RV 1120	Greece	4.63297849	-0.020148694	-0.030751691
RV 1122	Greece	4.53963771	0.073192085	0.029069846
RV 1123	Greece	4.65612728	-0.043297487	0.004454931
RV 1842	Greece	4.71627723	-0.103447437	0.001590381
RV 1845	Greece	4.46847856	0.144351229	0.025266115
RV 1846	Greece	4.54477543	0.068054357	0.032878948
RV 1847	Greece	4.55282024	0.060009552	0.000044200

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.32 to S3.36 (continued on next page)
2D Size and Shape Analysis – Hypothesis Testing, Sex-known Samples

Tab. S3.32: Two-way ANOVA table (type II tests) of all FML measurements as response variable including only the sex-known individuals per population. * = significant p-value.

Predictor	Sum of squares	Df	F-value	Pr(>F), p-value
Predictor 1: Population	20.18	3	0.9742	0.40952
Predictor 2: Sex	26.35	1	3.8155	0.05451
Interaction: Population : Sex	18.86	3	0.9105	0.44012
Residuals	517.92	75		

Tab. S3.33: Two-way ANOVA table (type II tests) of all FMB measurements as response variable including only the sex-known individuals per population. * = significant p-value.

Predictor	Sum of squares	Df	F-value	Pr(>F) , p-value
Predictor 1: Population	45.21	3	3.2318	0.02702*
Predictor 2: Sex	9.93	1	2.1300	0.14862
Interaction: Population : Sex	12.23	3	0.8740	0.45851
Residuals	349.74	75		

Tab. S3.34: Two-way ANOVA table (type II tests) of all FMI measurements as response variable including only the sex-known individuals per population. * = significant p-value.

Predictor	Sum of squares	Df	F-value	Pr(>F) , p-value
Predictor 1: Population	266.24	3	3.1959	0.02822*
Predictor 2: Sex	11.81	1	0.4253	0.51631
Interaction: Population : Sex	32.05	3	0.3847	0.76431
Residuals	2082.66	75		

Tab. S3.35: Tukey's HSD post hoc test results (Tukey multiple comparisons of means 95% family-wise confidence level) of the significant population term in the two-way FMB ANOVA analysis. * = significant p-value.

Population pairs	Difference	Lower	Upper	Adjusted p-value
Germany-Eritrea	1.7233709	0.1545882	3.292154	0.0256286*
Greece-Eritrea	1.0378947	-0.9606574	3.036447	0.5253348
Japan-Eritrea	2.0778947	-0.3135448	4.469334	0.1111939
Greece-Germany	-0.6854762	-2.4365509	1.065599	0.7332778
Japan-Germany	0.3545238	-1.8343196	2.543367	0.9739290
Japan-Greece	1.0400000	-1.4747896	3.554790	0.6987295

Tab. S3.36: Tukey's HSD post hoc test results (Tukey multiple comparisons of means 95% family-wise confidence level) of the significant population term in the two-way FMI ANOVA analysis. * = significant p-value.

Population pairs	Difference	Lower	Upper	Adjusted p-value
Germany-Eritrea	3.1351504	-0.6930809	6.963382	0.1464446
Greece-Eritrea	4.0937218	-0.7832567	8.970700	0.1310957
Japan-Eritrea	6.1453289	0.3096045	11.981053	0.0351305*
Greece-Germany	0.9585714	-3.3144989	5.231642	0.9349784
Japan-Germany	3.0101786	-2.3311593	8.351516	0.4540812
Japan-Greece	2.0516071	-4.0851229	8.188337	0.8159994

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.37 to S3.41 (continued on next page)
2D Size and Shape Analysis – Hypothesis Testing, Entire Sample

Tab. S3.37: One-way ANOVA table (type II tests) of all FML measurements as response variable including all individuals per population. * = significant p-value.

Predictor	Sum of squares	Df	F-value	Pr(>F), p-value
Population	16.41	3	0.797	0.4985
Residuals	645.11	94		

Tab. S3.38: One-way ANOVA table (type II tests) of all FMB measurements as response variable including all individuals per population. * = significant p-value.

Predictor	Sum of squares	Df	F-value	Pr(>F), p-value
Population	60.07	3	4.0493	0.009374*
Residuals	464.80	94		

Tab. S3.39: One-way ANOVA table (type II tests) of all FMI measurements as response variable including all individuals per population. * = significant p-value.

Predictor	Sum of squares	Df	F-value	Pr(>F), p-value
Population	293.9	3	3.5349	0.01773*
Residuals	2605.1	94		

Tab. S3.40: Tukey's HSD post hoc test results (Tukey multiple comparisons of means 95% family-wise confidence level) of the significant population term in the one-way FMB ANOVA analysis of the entire, sex-pooled dataset (see tab. S3.38). * = significant p-value.

Population pairs	Difference	Lower	Upper	Adjusted p-value
Germany-Eritrea	2.0127211	0.4957431	3.529699	0.0043068*
Greece-Eritrea	1.4245938	-0.4729667	3.322154	0.2091991
Japan-Eritrea	1.6413853	-0.5233608	3.806131	0.2016564
Greece-Germany	-0.5881273	-2.2252733	1.049019	0.7836137
Japan-Germany	-0.3713358	-2.3118606	1.569189	0.9587538
Japan-Greece	0.2167914	-2.0337974	2.467380	0.9943499

Tab. S3.41: Tukey's HSD post hoc test results (Tukey multiple comparisons of means 95% family-wise confidence level) of the significant population term in the one-way FMI ANOVA analysis of the entire, sex-pooled dataset (see tab. S3.39). * = significant p-value.

Population pairs	Difference	Lower	Upper	Adjusted p-value
Germany-Eritrea	3.91360544	0.32223496	7.504976	0.0270805*
Greece-Eritrea	3.95675070	-0.53563014	8.449132	0.1044737
Japan-Eritrea	5.20562771	0.08069844	10.330557	0.0450576*
Greece-Germany	0.04314526	-3.83271708	3.919008	0.9999911
Japan-Germany	1.29202226	-3.30207429	5.886119	0.8825120
Japan-Greece	1.24887701	-4.07928092	6.577035	0.9276877

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.42 to S3.43

3D GM Shape Analysis – Hypothesis Testing

Tab. S3.42: One-way Procrustes shape ANOVA table (Goodall's F-test) of the Procrustes distances per population of the entire, sex-pooled dataset (n = 98). * = significant p-value.

Predictor	Df	SS	MS	Rsqr (R ²)	F-value	Z-value	Pr(>F) p-value
Population	3	0.01532	0.0051070	0.03906	1.2735	1.096	0.17
Residuals	94	0.37696	0.0040102	0.96094			
Total	97	0.39228					

Tab. S3.43: Two-way Procrustes shape ANOVA table (Goodall's F-test) of the Procrustes distances per population of the sex-known dataset (n = 83). * = significant p-value.

Predictor	Df	SS	MS	Rsqr (R ²)	F-value	Z-value	Pr(>F) p-value
Sex	1	0.00301	0.0030140	0.00936	0.7708	-0.43875	0.667
Population	3	0.01395	0.0046513	0.04333	1.1895	0.87509	0.187
Interaction	3	0.01184	0.0039465	0.03676	1.1895	0.14694	0.434
Residuals	75	0.29326	0.0039102	0.91056			
Total	82	0.32207					

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.44 to S3.45

3D GM Form Analysis – Allometric Regression, Hypothesis Testing

Tab. S3.44: Results of the ANCOVA using Goodall's F-test based on the ordinary least squares estimation method and null model residual randomization (1.000 permutations) for the entire dataset (n = 98) for interpopulation comparison. * = significant p-value (p < 0.05).

Group	ResDf	Df	RSS	SS	MS	R ²	F	Z	P (Pr>F)
Proc. coord. ~ lnCS (Null model)	96	1	0.38987						
Proc. coord. ~ lnCS + Population (common allometry model)	93	3	0.37389	0.015977	0.0053255	0.040727	1.3246	1.30287	0.094
Proc. coord. ~ lnCS * Population (unique allometry model)	90	6	0.36446	0.025414	0.0042356	0.064785	1.0460	0.36566	0.347
Total	97		0.39228						

ab. S3.45: Results of the ANCOVA using Goodall's F-test based on the ordinary least squares estimation method and null model residual randomization (1.000 permutations) for the sex-known dataset (n = 83) for intra-inter-population comparison. * = significant p-value (p < 0.05).

Group	ResDf	Df	RSS	SS	MS	R ²	F	Z	P (Pr>F)
Proc. coord. ~ lnCS (Null model)	81	1	0.31894			0.000000			
Proc. coord. ~ lnCS + Sex * Population (common allometry model)	74	7	0.28987	0.029061	0.0041516	0.090232	1.0598	0.47644	0.321
Proc. coord. ~ lnCS * Sex * Population (unique allometry model)	67	14	0.26137	0.057567	0.0041119	0.178738	1.0541	0.49834	0.314
Total	82		0.32207						

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.46

FML Mean, Standard Deviation and Range Distribution across Populations

Figure S3.46: Univariate plot showing the spectrum of FML means (centre points), standard deviations from the means (dark grey lines) and minimum to maximum ranges (coloured lines) across all ordered FM reference summary statistics including the new Berlin data (blue filled point shapes: triangle (up) = female group, triangle (down) = male group, square = sex-pooled group). Blue filled point shapes represent mean values of the newly analysed Berlin samples. Sex-pooled samples included sex-unknown individuals in the newly analysed populations.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.47

FMB Mean, Standard Deviation and Range Distribution across Populations

Figure S3.47: Univariate plot showing the spectrum of FMB means (centre points), standard deviations from the means (dark grey lines) and minimum to maximum ranges (coloured lines) across all ordered FM reference summary statistics including the new Berlin data (blue filled point shapes: triangle (up) = female group, triangle (down) = male group, square = sex-pooled group). Blue filled point shapes represent mean values of the newly analysed Berlin samples. Sex-pooled samples included sex-unknown individuals in the newly analysed populations.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.48

FMI Mean, Standard Deviation and Range Distribution across populations

Figure S3.48: Univariate plot showing the spectrum of FMI means (centre points), standard deviations from the means (dark grey lines) and minimum to maximum ranges (coloured lines) across all ordered FM reference summary statistics including the new Berlin data (blue filled point shapes: triangle (up) = female group, triangle (down) = male group, square = sex-pooled group). Blue filled point shapes represent mean values of the newly analysed Berlin samples. Sex-pooled samples included sex-unknown individuals in the newly analysed populations. Vertical grey-dotted lines enclose the intermediate FM shape spectrum, narrow FM's are to its left, wide to the right.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.49

Eritrea – FML versus FMB Distribution

Figure S3.49: Scatter and marginal box plots for all averaged physical FML versus FMB measurements and their sex-wise group means (x-hollow points) of the Eritrean subsample (n = 21). Point shape indicates assigned FMI category. Convex hulls enclose each sex group.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.50

Japan – FML versus FMB Distribution

Intrapopulation comparison of FML versus FMB in the Japanese sample

Figure S3.50: Scatter and marginal box plots for all averaged physical FML versus FMB measurements and their sex-wise group means (x-hollow points) of the Japanese subsample (n = 11). Point shape indicates assigned FMI category. Convex hulls enclose each sex group.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.51

Germany – FML versus FMB Distribution

Figure S3.51: Scatter and marginal box plots for all averaged physical FML versus FMB measurements and their sex-wise group means (x-hollow points) of the German subsample (n = 49). Point shape indicates assigned FMI category. Convex hulls enclose each sex group.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.52

Greece – FML versus FMB Distribution

Figure S3.52: Scatter and marginal box plots for all averaged physical FML versus FMB measurements and their sex-wise group means (x-hollow points) of the Greek subsample (n = 17). Point shape indicates assigned FMI category. Convex hulls enclose each sex group.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.53

Entire Dataset – FML versus FMB Distribution between Sexes

Figure S3.53: Scatter and marginal box plots for all averaged physical FML versus FMB measurements and their sex-wise group means (x-hollow points) of the entire dataset ($n = 98$). Point shape indicates assigned FMI category. Convex hulls enclose each sex group.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.54 and S3.55

Mean FML versus FMB Distribution across Populations – Reference Data

Figure S3.54: Scatter plot of sex-separated mean FML versus FMB values taken from the published FM reference literature including the new Berlin samples (*). Specific point and convex hulls colors are used to highlight data from different continents: Africa = blue, Asia = red, (South) America = yellow, Europe = green.

Figure S3.55: Scatter plot of sex-pooled mean FML versus FMB values taken from the published FM reference literature including the new Berlin samples (*). Specific point and convex hulls colors are used to highlight data from different continents: Africa = blue, Asia = red, (North/South) America = yellow, Europe = green.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.56

Mean FML versus FMB Distribution between Sexes across Populations – Reference Data

Figure S3.56: Scatter plot of sex-separated mean FML versus FMB values taken from the published FM reference literature including the new Berlin samples. Darkgrey convex hulls = female subgroup cluster, lightgrey convex hulls = male subgroup cluster. New Berlin samples included (*). Base plot is the same as in fig. S3.54.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.57

Entire Dataset – FML versus FMB against FMI Distribution

Figure S3.57: Scatter and marginal box plots for all averaged physical FML versus FMB measurements in relation to the FMI shape category distribution of the entire dataset ($n = 98$). Point shape indicates assigned FMI category. Convex hulls enclose each FMI shape category group. x-hollow points = FML-to-FMB group mean per FMI shape category.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.58 and S3.59

Interpopulation FMI Shape Category Frequencies among the Berlin Samples

FMI shape category frequencies across populations

Figure S3.58: Advanced contingency chart plot of the absolute FMI shape category frequencies across the populations. Relative frequencies are reported in table S3.70.

Tab. S3.59: Absolute and relative population-wise frequencies of FMI categories among the Berlin samples.

FMI Category	Eritrea		Japan		Germany		Greece	
Narrow	11	52.38%	1	9.09%	17	34.39%	6	35.29%
Intermediate	7	33.33%	6	54.55%	12	24.49%	4	23.53%
Wide	3	14.29%	4	36.36%	20	40.82%	7	41.18%
Total	21	100%	11	100%	49	100%	17	100%

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.60 and S3.61

Intrapopulation FMI Shape Category Frequencies among the Berlin Samples

Figure S3.60: Advanced contingency chart plot of the sex-wise absolute FMI shape category frequencies across the populations. Relative frequencies are reported in table S3.72.

Tab. S3.61: Absolute and relative sex-wise frequencies of FMI categories among the Berlin samples.

Population	Sex	Narrow		Intermediate		Wide		Total
Eritrea	Female	3	37.50%	2	25.00%	3	37.50%	8
Eritrea	Male	6	50.00%	5	41.67%	1	8.33%	12
Japan	Female	0	0%	2	50.00%	2	50.00%	4
Japan	Male	0	0%	2	50.00%	2	50.00%	4
Germany	Female	6	31.58%	7	36.84%	6	31.58%	19
Germany	Male	10	43.48%	4	17.39%	9	39.13%	23
Greece	Female	3	42.86%	1	14.29%	3	42.86%	7
Greece	Male	1	14.29%	3	42.86%	3	42.86%	7

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.62

3D GM Shape-PCA – Entire Dataset

Fig. S3.62: Unstandardized Procrustes shape PC score plot of the entire, sex-pooled sample showing PC1 (accounting for 22.89% of the explained variance) and PC2 (accounting for 12.94% of the explained variance) and minimum and maximum wireframe deformations of the landmark configuration from the mean shape along each axis. Convex hulls enclose each population. X-hollow scatter points represent PC score population group means.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.63

3D GM Shape-PCA – Entire Dataset

Fig. S3.63: Unstandardized Procrustes shape PC score plot of the entire, sex-pooled sample showing PC3 (accounting for 9.70% of the explained variance) and PC4 (accounting for 8.25% of the explained variance) and minimum and maximum wireframe deformations of the landmark configuration from the mean shape along each axis. Convex hulls enclose each population. X-hollow scatter points represent PC score population group means.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.64

3D GM Shape-PCA – Sex-known Dataset

Fig. S3.64: Unstandardized Procrustes shape PC score plot of the entire, sex-pooled sample showing PC1 (accounting for 20.19% of the explained variance) and PC2 (accounting for 13.89% of the explained variance) and minimum and maximum wireframe deformations of the landmark configuration from the mean shape along each axis. Convex hulls enclose each sex-group. X-hollow scatter points represent PC score sex-group means.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.65

3D GM Shape-PCA – Sex-known Dataset

Fig. S3.65: Unstandardized Procrustes shape PC score plot of the entire, sex-pooled sample showing PC3 (accounting for 10.57% of the explained variance) and PC4 (accounting for 8.84% of the explained variance) and minimum and maximum wireframe deformations of the landmark configuration from the mean shape along each axis. Convex hulls enclose each sex-group. X-hollow scatter points represent PC score sex-group means.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.66

3D GM Form-PCA – Entire Dataset

Fig. S3.66: Unstandardized Procrustes form PC score plot and biplot of the entire, sex-pooled sample showing PC1 (accounting for 19.23% of the explained variance) and PC2 (accounting for 17.76% of the explained variance). Convex hulls enclose each population. X-hollow scatter points represent PC score sex-group means.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.67

3D GM Form-PCA – Sex-known Dataset

Fig. S3.67: Unstandardized Procrustes form PC score plot and biplot of the sex-known sample showing PC1 (accounting for 20.26% of the explained variance) and PC2 (accounting for 14.92% of the explained variance). Convex hulls enclose each population. X-hollow scatter points represent PC score sex-group means.

Supplementary Material, Results – S3.68

3D GM Form Analysis – PLS Analysis of the Sex-separated Dataset

Figure. S3.68: Two-block partial least square analysis plot and test results of the sex-known dataset. X-hollow points = sex means. Note that the reported test statistics refer to the overall sex-pooled regression line that is not shown here. Coloured lines = individual sex-group per population regression lines.